

FUTURE MIGRATION
SCENARIOS FOR EUROPE

Case Study

TUNISIA

Drivers and trajectories of migration to Europe

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

ANPEJ Agence Nationale pour la Promotion de l'Emploi des Jeunes
ANSD Agence Nationale de la Statistique et de la Démographie
AU African Union
CIRAD Centre de Coopération Internationale en Recherche Agronomique pour le Développement
ENDA Prospectives Dialogues Politiques
EU European Union
FAO Fonds des Nations Unies pour l'Alimentation et l'Agriculture
GPHC : General Population and Housing Census
IFAD International Fund for Agricultural Development
INS: Institut National de la Statistique/ National Statistics Institute (Tunisia)
IOM International Organisation for Migration
IPAR Initiative Prospective agricole et rurale
IPCC Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IRD Institut de recherche pour le développement
KR-I Kurdistan Iraqi Region
LPS Lettre de Politique Sectorielle
LPSEDD Lettre de Politique du Secteur de l'Environnement et du Développement durable
MAESE Ministère des Affaires Étrangères et des Sénégalais de l'Extérieur
MEDD Ministère de l'Environnement et du Développement Durable
OIM Organisation Internationale pour les Migrations
ONU Organisation des Nations Unies
OTE (Office des Tunisiens à l'Etranger/ Tunisiens' Abroad Office)
PANAUDIT Panafricaine d'Audit
PKK Kurdistan Workers' Party
PSE Plan Sénégal Emergent
PSO Plan Stratégique et Opérationnel
RGPHAE Recensement Général de la Population, de l'Habitat, de l'Agriculture et de l'Elevage
UN United Nations
USAID US Agency for International Development
WB World Bank

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Drivers and Trajectories of Migration to Europe

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1. Introduction

Objectives and justification of the study

The research carried in Tunisia aimed to add to general aims of FUME project. Therefore the main objective of this report is to present the decision-making practices that drive potential migrants to leave the areas of origin as well as to settle in or move forward from Sousse city. Black et al. (2011) identified 'five families of drivers which affect migration decisions: economic, political, social, demographic and environmental' arguing that those drivers operate in combination and the role of the environment depends on the remaining. Within the framework, we compare and contrast the role of listed factors influencing migration decision making in a local context.

This aim is achieved by answer for the following research questions:

- How the interaction of different forms of mobility and their changes over time affect the motivations to leave areas of origin and "stepping points" such as Sousse city?
- What is the role of the Sousse city in shaping decision on migration abroad for many internal migrants from rural villages and small towns who arrived to the city at different times?
- What are possible future scenarios of Tunisian's migration to Europe?

With 11,8 millions of inhabitants, Tunisia is a small North African country in the heart of the central Mediterranean. Internal and international migration (emigration, immigration, transit, temporary migration or definitive settlement of foreigners) are part of the migration personality of Tunisia. As the research area for analysis was chosen Sousse city. It is the third greatest city in Tunisia and the regional metropolis of the 'Sahel'¹ Region². In 2014, the population of Sousse Commune counted 239,124 inhabitants (Source: INS. RGPH, 2015 p. 190). If the Great Sousse agglomeration is taken into account its population is over two times higher (520,000) than the population of the city of Sousse. (INS, 2015).

Sousse exerts a strong attraction on the whole region of the Sahel and on the neighbouring region of the Centre-West (Governorates of Kasserine and Kairouan and Sidi Bouzid) areas, where in the 2011 broke out uprisings. 65% of migrants who came to Sousse governorate during last 15 years installed themselves in Sousse agglomeration (Fig 2).

Sousse plays an important role in the migration trajectories of Tunisia. Because of its size and its directional and polarising functions, Sousse attracts many migrants who can be classified in three categories: 1) Tunisian immigrants from the interior regions; 2) Tunisian immigrants returning from abroad; and, 3) foreigners coming, mainly, from sub-Saharan Africa, other Maghreb countries or Europe. Within this report, we are going to focus on the first of the given categories of migrants. Within this category, we distinguish three types of migrants 1) newcomers - those who came to

¹ In Tunisia, the term "Sahel" refers to the coastal region covered by the governorates of Sousse, Monastir and Mahdia. It's not linked to the African "Sahel" area which extend on the Southern Shore of the Great Sahara from Senegal in the West to the Horn of Africa in the East.

² Governorates of Sousse, Monastir and Mahdia with a total of 1,634,611 inhabitants in 2014.

Sousse within the last five years, 2) longstayers - who came to Sousse between 5 and 10 years ago, and 3) settled migrants - those who came to Sousse more than 10 years ago.

The description of Tunisian case study is divided into two main sections: the first one is dedicated to the results of the literature review which describes push and pull and hold back factors of migration from Tunisia to Europe and particularly as the first step from Tunisian rural areas to Sousse. The factors are organised into the following subsections: environmental conditions, demographic situation, socio-cultural context, economic situation and last but not least political circumstances that may cause migration. The second section presents results of the research carried in Sousse with the focus on the reasons of departure from the origins and how it was changing in time, the perception of the current situation in the city of Sousse and finally the future intention to move forward, stay or return to the area of origin. Some thought on further areas worth to be investigated are given at the end of this part.

Picture: Chermity Mohamed/Unsplash.com

2. Field area of research - The region of Grand Sousse, Tunisia

The Tunisia fieldwork was carried out in the city of Sousse and in its suburbs between January and October 2021. The choice of Sousse is related to the role that the city plays in the country, its economy and its importance in migration processes on national and international levels. It is also the third-largest governorate in the country after Grand Tunis and Sfax. In 2014, it had a population of 674,9712 inhabitants. It is an industrial city with 528 companies operating mainly in the textile and clothing industry, the food industry and the mechanical and electrical industries. The governorate of Sousse is also the second-largest tourist hub in Tunisia. The Centre-East of the country, and in particular Sousse, is an area that attracts internal migrants. These migrants generally come from the so-called interior regions, i.e. the three western provinces (Kairouan, Kasserine and Sidi Bouzid), which are considered repulsive because of high rates of unemployment and poverty (Fig. 1) These inequalities also affect the different communes and districts of Sousse. Unsurprisingly, the majority of internal migrants-which is represented in the sample- settle in the outskirts of the city where rent is cheaper.

Figure 1. Tunisia Administrative map.

Source: <https://fr.mapsofworld.com/tunisie/>

Within the Tunisian case study, we have conducted 29 in-depth interviews with migrants (13 of whom were men and 16 women) and 5 interviews with experts. The age of the interviewees ranged between 22 and 62 years. Among the interviewees, 3 people were unemployed or looking after the household, 3 were working as white collars, 5 were students, 7 were day workers, unskilled workers, skilled workers or craftsmen, and 11 were service employees or salespeople, office workers, technicians and other middle personnel.

The identification and selection of the informants were made by adopting the "snowball" approach and a non-participant observation method. First, the field researchers mobilised their network and contacts to find the requested profiles. Secondly, to facilitate the search for participants they reached the interviewees through so-called gatekeepers - two street animators. Street animators are young people whose tasks are to accompany the young people of the neighbourhood and to coordinate between the inhabitants and the local authorities. The two street animators helped particularly in the Taffala neighbourhood, which is a popular area that attracts many internal migrants (Fig.2; see also Fig.1).

Figure 2. Location of suburbs of Sousse where IDIs were conducted

Blue line: limits of concerned Suburbs and urban sectors. Red Line: Small urban sectors into big Suburbs

Source: Hassen Boubakri's elaboration

The interviews were conducted in Tunisian Darija with the use of a semi-structured in-depth interview scenario. In each interview, the research group explained to the participant the scope of the research, its objectives, and the different clauses of the consent. The interviews lasted between half an hour and two hours. The researchers insisted on the need for recording and the signing of the consent. Except for two persons, the participants agreed to sign the consent because they trusted the researchers or the intermediary persons. In case of lack of signed consent, an oral one was recorded. Despite two interviews, which were conducted via zoom, all the other interviews were conducted face-to-face. All the conducted interviews were recorded after the consent was signed, transcribed, translated into English and coded with the use of the NVivo tool.

The most significant challenges that the research team faced during the research were:

- Ensuring representativeness and variation of characteristics of interviewees - finding people who were already settled was easier than finding new migrants, who were less visible. In addition, skilled migrants are less present in the sample.
- Carrying out the fieldwork on schedule - due to the COVID pandemic and the confinements detected by the authorities the fieldwork team was forced to postpone the fieldwork for several days on a few occasions. Finally, the fieldwork was postponed by half a year. In the interviews carried out, the research group respected regulations related to the pandemic by wearing masks and keeping the distance to avoid a health risk for the interviewers and the interviewees. The interviews were carried out in the participants' homes, workplaces and cafés.

- In addition to the pandemic, local riots took place at the beginning of and in July 2021. The fieldwork started at the end of December 2020. This period marked the celebration of the 2011 revolution. Because of the economic and social crisis and the corruption of the political class, angry demonstrations broke out in different parts of the country where the police responded to stone-throwing with tear gas. This violence took place in several cities in Tunisia (Tunis, Bizerte, Menzel Bourguiba, Sousse and Nabeul, Kasserine and Siliana), despite the establishment of a lockdown with a curfew at 4 pm, against the spread of Covid-19. According to the version of the Ministry of Interior, more than 600 people have already been arrested. The Ministry referred to groups of people between 15 and 25 years old who “burnt tyres and rubbish bins in order to obstruct the movements of the security forces”, as well as looting. In Sousse, clashes broke out in several towns and neighbourhoods, namely Cité Erriadh, Taffela, Bir chebek, Bouhsina, M’saken, Gabadji, Bebhhar etc. All this caused additional troubles for the field research in investigated regions and among the chosen population.

- Sensitivity of the topic - the issue of internal migration is sensitive in Tunisia. Some migrants feel marginalised, humiliated, and rejected by the local population. This is why, when explaining the research, some migrants laughed and said “you want to work on us “nouzouh” (exodus)? This normalisation hides on the one hand an internalised stigma and on the other hand a strategy to cope with the difficulties of adaptation. This creates a sensitive relationship between participants and researchers as the latter try to make questions related to migration experience without hurting the feelings of participants. Despite the clear information that was delivered to the interviewees before the interview, some of them expected incentives or clearly asked for service after the interview. This raised the issue of the “give and take” relationship. Additionally, some of the interviews were emotionally charged, with some participants crying and others displaying various emotions.

2.1 The existing and historical migration scenario to/from Tunisia and Sousse particularly

Tunisia is an Arab-Muslim country, with a tiny Berber minority (1 to 2% of its population). It used to be a province of the Ottoman Empire from the 16th century until the establishment of the French protectorate (1881). Tunisia has been independent since 1956. At the crossroads of influences in the heart of the Mediterranean, Tunisia has a real migratory personality within the Maghreb area, according to its pre-colonial and colonial past, but also to the evolution of a society in rapid transition, open to the world but faced to many economic and social challenges. In the mid-1970s, the crisis and suspension of immigration in France, and in other main destination countries of Tunisian migrants, such as Germany and the Benelux, were a major turning point for the redeployment of the Tunisian migratory field towards other horizons (Libya, Gulf Countries, North America) (Boubakri, H; Simon, G. 2015).

More recently, its geographical position close the European territory (the Italian Lampedusa is 80 miles far from the Tunisian coast), has favoured the development of transit migration from sub-Saharan Africa. However, for the last two decades, Tunisia has gradually become the destination and the place of settlement for foreign populations originating from neighbouring Maghreb countries, Europe and sub-Saharan Africa (Boubakri 2006, 2009, 2013 a, b, 2016). The INS counted 53 490 foreign residents in Tunisia in 2014, against 28 100 in 2004 (INS, 2008; 2017).

Tunisia has always been, and remains, a country of departure of its own migrants. 1.5 million Tunisians are living abroad in 2018 (OTE, 2019), which represented 12,8 % of the resident population in Tunisia itself. More than 8 Tunisian emigrants out of ten (82.3%) are settled in Europe, and 2/3 of these ones live in France (Ibid). The revolution of 2011 has turned the existing migratory situation upside down without, however, deeply changing the main destination of the flows or modifying the fundamental features of this form of mobility (Boubakri, 2013a, b).

The new patterns of International Migration in Tunisia

Migration occupies a central place in the daily lives of Tunisians. Situated in the heart of the Mediterranean, opposite Italy, Tunisia has always been a land of destination, passage or arrival of human flows, trade and good exchanges. It concerns all social categories, rich and poor, and all regions and cities of the country (Boubakri, 2021a). The international migration is the one that receives more attention, mostly due to its constant growth, European interest and remittances flow which fuel Tunisian economy.

One of the characteristics of international migration data in Tunisia is their lack of homogeneity and reliability. There are large disparities in the figures depending on the body producing the data. According to the OTE (Office des Tunisiens à l'étranger/Tunisians Abroad's Office: TAO), the number of Tunisians living abroad increased systematically. In 2009, they were 1,1 Million and in 2017 they were 1,4 Million (Flayols, Jongerius and de Bel-Air, 2019, OTE, 2019). The National Institute of Statistics (INS/NIS) counted 66 000 Tunisians leaving for abroad in five years (2009-2014), i.e. an annual average of 13 200. According to Tunisian Labour Market Panel Survey carried out in 2014 (Assaad et al., 2016), migrants represent slightly more than 12,8 percent of the whole country's resident population. In 2020 the net migration rate in Tunisia is estimated for -1.4 migrants/1000 population (MPI, 2020). More recent data were published in December 2021, following the results of the first Tunisian survey on international migration in the country, the "Tunisia HIMS"³. 566,000 Tunisians over the age of 15 were living abroad on that date (388,000 men and 178,000 women, i.e. a ratio of 68/32%). There is a strong geographical concentration of regions of origin in Tunisia as for the countries of destination: ¾ of migrants come from three regions (Greater Tunis, North-East and Center-East). ¾ of migrants are concentrated in three destination countries (France, Italy and Germany). This is a fairly young population: 40% are between 15 and 29 years old. Their level of education is higher than that of the population living in Tunisia: 1/3 are university graduates. The discrepancies in the count of Tunisians residing abroad pose an acute problem for decision-makers, while the producers of this type of data are Ministries (of the Interior, of Foreign Affairs) or public bodies for the most of them (TAO, NIS).

With such a number of Tunisians living abroad, Tunisia was and still is, one of the significant emigration countries in the Mediterranean (Ministère des Affaires Sociales, 2014; Natter, 2015; Flayols, Jongerius and de Bel-Air, 2019). Thanks to the transfers of their incomes, Tunisian migrants contribute to the financial balances with about 5 to 6% of the Gross National Product (GNP) (BCT, 2021).

The destination of migration has changed over time. The two decades from 1990 to 2010 were marked by the emergence of Italy and France as major destination countries for irregular migrants from North Africa, following the signing of the Schengen Agreement and its subsequent implementation in the single space. Since that time both countries have carried out successive and massive regularisations of irregular migrants. The number of Tunisians in Italy is today about 200 000 people.

With around 120,000 migrants in 2010, Libya became the third country of destination for Tunisians after France and Italy. But since 2011, civil war, chaos and the reign of armed groups and militias have profoundly reduced the number of Tunisians still working in Libya. Between February and October 2011, 105,865 Tunisian emigrants returned home (IOM, 2011, Boubakri and Simon, 2015). In 2017, France represented the 1st destination with 42% of the total.

According to the data of the Ministry of Social Affairs, Tunisian international migration is dominated by men. In 2014 they constituted two-thirds of the migrant population. The gender dimension change in time and space, however women's participation to some destinations is relatively high compared to previous decades.

³ "Tunisia HIMS" (Households International Migration Survey) was carried out in 2020- 2021 by the National Institute of Statistics (INS), in collaboration with the National Observatory of Migration (ONM), with the support of the International Center for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD)

They represent 46% of departures to France and other countries, but only 9% of departures to Italy (INS, 2017). Migrants are also young. In those years, almost half (45.8%) of those living abroad were under 25 years old, and 39% of those were under the age of 16. This is mostly due to the second generation as around 20% of those staying abroad were binational. The return of Tunisians residing abroad was almost 30 000 in five years, i.e. an annual average of 6,000 persons/year (INS, 2017. Ibid).

According to the declaration of Tunisian migrants in Italy, their main reasons for migration are linked to work (70 percent of total sample) and improvement of living conditions such as access to health care and better education conditions (50 percent). Significant number also declared matrimony (around 13 percent, usually women), reduction of the income from agriculture activity (11 percent) and finally studies (10 percent) (Zuccotti et al., 2018, p. 26). The last one has doubled in comparison with the research from the beginning of the XXI century, when education was mentioned by 5,5 percent of respondents (Sabadie et al., 2010). The reasons behind women’s decision are slightly different. Their migration is mostly related to family issues – they follow their husband or father. The single female migration is rather rare. Those who decide for this are migrating in order to finalise their education or realise their professional goal. They usually come from wealthy families and join a member who has already migrated (Kriaa and El Elj, 2013; Zuccotti et al., 2018).

Final important domain is that of highly skilled individuals. In the case of Tunisia, in 2011, 19,9% of the migrants in OECD countries was tertiary educated (World Bank, 2016). In 2000, the emigration rate of the tertiary educated was about 13% in Tunisia (World Bank, 2011, p. 29), so we can clearly observe increase in this area, the reason of which will be further elaborated.

Irregular emigration from Tunisia

In 14 years (2009-2022), more than 100,000 irregular migrants have landed on the Italian coasts from Tunisia (Italian Ministry of the Interior). 73,860 (i.e. 76%) had landed in 4 years (28,013 in 2011 and 45,847 in the three years 2020, 2021 and the first ten months of 2022) (Fig. 3). Therefore, there is an acceleration in landings from 2020, the year of the outbreak of the Covid-19 health crisis. But the number of irregulars is not limited to that of landings (over 45,000 in 3 years). To this first number must be added the number of migrants intercepted by Tunisian security (65,440) during failed operations (fig. 4).

Figure 3. Number of irregular migrants from Tunisia who landed on Italian Coasts (2009-2022)
Source: Italian Ministry of Interior

Figure 4. Irregular Migrants crossing the Mediterranean from Tunisia in 2020 to 2022: arrivals and interceptions
 Source: Italian Ministry of Interior & Tunisian Sea Guards

In 2020, the number of migrants who have landed on Italian coasts was close to that of interceptions before arrival in Italy (49/51%). In 2021 and 2022, interceptions represent 62% of crossings, while 38% of migrants succeed in disembarking in Italy. This is due to two reasons: the surge in the total number of irregular migrants (landings and interceptions combined), i.e. 110,000 in 3 years and the increase in the number of interceptions, which rose from 26,349 in 2020 to 41,324 in 2021 and 42,612 in the first 10 months of 2022.

This is presented as a success by the Tunisian authorities and reflects Tunisia's integration of standards for the outsourcing of European border control to the region' third countries, including Tunisia. The Tunisian authorities may consider their involvement as an additional source of legitimacy vis-à-vis the EU and its member states.

These figures have never been reached since the beginning of the phenomenon of irregular migration in the late 1980s of the 20th century. In 2020, the governorate of Sfax represents the most important departure location (43.47%), followed by Tunis (26.08%), Nabeul and Mahdia (13.04%) and Monastir (4.34%) (IB, 2021). Tunisia has been going through an acute socio-economic crisis for at least five years, coupled with a political and institutional crisis following the coup by the current President K. Saeid. The repercussions of this multiple crisis affect the population in its daily life: shortages of food and medicine, two-digit inflation, weakened capacities of the State to meet the needs of the population, public deficits leading to difficulties for the State to finance the development and reduce social and regional inequalities. There is indeed a feeling of generalised disenchantment that affects whole social classes and results in a pronounced erosion of the trust in the future and in the Politics. Irregular migration and Skills migration are symptoms that do not deceive the magnitude of this multiple crisis that the country is going through. In 10 years (2011-2020), 100,000 higher education graduates have left Tunisia, including thousands of doctors and tens of thousands of engineers and technicians. Faced with such a quest for migration, Tunisians who do not have the education background and skills to migrate regularly, do so irregularly (see above) which arouses the appetite of migrant smuggling networks and causes tragedies of shipwrecks that affect the poorest families who have sent their children in search of "El Dorado".

Sousse area: One of the most attractive area on the Tunisian coastline

Until the end of the 1960s, the Sousse region had a negative net migration, such as all the other regions of Tunisia, except Tunis, which was the only governorate having a surplus net migration (+202,000 migrants was de Tunis governorate's net migration in 1966) (INS, 1966). It is only since the 1970s that the region of Sousse has become attractive to migrants, and therefore has a surplus, like the other coastal regions from Tunis in the North to Djerba in the South. Since 1975, the Centre-East's region (to which the governorate of Sousse belongs) has always doubled and sometimes tripled its net migration surplus from one decade to the next (Tab 1).

Table 1. Evolution of the balance sheet, and of the internal migration surplus, of the governorate and city of Sousse (1966-2014)

	1966	1975	1984	1994	2004	2014
City of Sousse	-	-	-	-	13 432	1 025
Governorat of Sousse	- 35 097	300	5 800	8 232	21 863	15 100

The city of Sousse, known as "Jawharat essahil" (The Pearl of the Sahel), has attracted large internal migratory flows from the rural areas of its immediate hinterland (governorates of Sousse, Monastir and Mahdia), and especially from the Central West, whose negative net migration have continued to grow during the same period (Table 1 and 2, & Fig. 5). Only during 10 years (2x5) (in 1999-2004 and then in 2009-2014) the city of Sousse alone has received 73 351 internal migrants, which represents 61.5 percent of all the 119 952 internal migrants who entered the governorate of Sousse during the same period. Two third of those who reach Sousse Governorate settle in the Great Sousse (INS, RGPH, 1966-2014). The governorate of Sousse has kept a migratory surplus (positive balance sheet) which has strengthened from one period to the other from 1979 to 2004 (Table 2).

Figure 5. Internal migration fluxes to governorate of Sousse from other governorates between 1999 and 2014. Concept by Hassen Boubakri and elaboration Makram, based on: INS GCPH 2008, 2017 Own elaboration based on: INS, 2008 p. 209, 2017

Table 2. Internal migratory balances in the governorate of Sousse and the neighbouring governorates of Western Centre West and East Centre, between 1966 and 2014

Source : INS, General Censuses, 1966-2014

Governorates	1961-1966	1969 - 1975	1979 - 1984	1989 - 1994	1999 - 2004	2009-2014
Sfax	- 7 627	-2 200	+ 600	+ 7 452	+ 11 392	+ 3 900
Monastir		+5 900	+ 3 300	+ 5 030	+ 16 954	+ 11 800
Mahdia	- 34 495	+2 200	- 900	- 2 069	- 2 452	- 1 800
Sousse		+ 300	5 800	+ 8 232	+ 21 863	+15 100
Kairouan	- 9 291	- 3 400	-6 200	- 11 519	- 22 984	-19 400
Kasserine	- 6 107	- 1 500	-4 400	- 6 918	- 16 923	-12 400
Sidi Bouzid		+ 1 500	-1 900	- 5 493	- 14 085	-7 500

The population of the municipality of Sousse has increased from 203,928 inhabitants in 2004 to 239,124 inhabitants in 2014, i.e. a small increase of 35,196 additional inhabitants in 10 years and a timid average of yearly growth (1.6%/year). Even stronger attracted the satellite municipalities of the municipality of Sousse that were the destination for migrants coming to the agglomeration. The population of Greater Sousse has increased from 375,836 inhabitants in 2004 to 519,972 inhabitants in 2014, i.e. 144,136 additional inhabitants and a strong annual growth average, the double that of 2004 (3.3%/year). This wave of migration has boosted informal settlements (out of any urban planning, with no building permits and with poor public equipments) on the southern outskirts of the city, such as Taffala, Sidi Abdelhamid, Houmet el Oued (City of the river), neighbourhoods in which we conducted our survey. Due to the exhaustion of the supply of building land and the steep rise in land prices in the areas closer to the city, more recent informal settlements have sprung up on the western outskirts of Sousse, such as Roummaniya.⁴

The main areas sending internal migratory flows to the governorate (and the city) of Sousse are located in the rural governorates of the Centre West (Kairouan, Kasserine, Sidi Bouzid), the Sahel (Mahdia) and the North West (Siliana), close to Sousse (fig. 5 and 6 and table 3). There are no data about the geographic origin (rural/urban) of migrants at the level of the Great Sousse; however, we can consider that also 2/3 of migrants reaching Sousse have a rural origin. For the implementation of the in-depth interviews we will focus on rural migrants in the suburbs of Sousse.

⁴ This informal settlement is located in the neighbouring commune of Kalaa S'ghira, which is part of Greater Sousse, but the majority of the active population works in the Commune of Sousse.

Figure 6. Entrants to the governorate of Sousse from other governorates (1999-2004)

Source: INS, 2008

Figure 7. Entrants to the governorate of Sousse from other governorates (2009-2014)

Source: INS, 2017

Table 3. Rate of rural populations in the main governorates sending internal flows to the governorate of Sousse in 2014.

Governorates		Total Pop	Rural Pop	% of Rural population
Interior governorates	Sidi Bouzid	429 912	313 484	72,9
	Kairouan	570 559	369 028	64,7
	Siliana	223 087	128 536	57,6
	Kasserine	439 243	247 899	56,4
	Zaghouan	176 945	99 551	56,3
Coastal governorates	Mahdia	410 812	223 008	54,3
	Sfax	955 421	359 693	37,6
	Tunisia	10 982 754	3 545 717	32,3
	Nabeul	787 920	251 950	32,0
	Sousse	674 971	127 568	18,9
	Monastir	548 828	0	0,0
	Tunis	1 056 247	0	0,0

Picture: Albina Andreeva/Unsplash.com

3. The context for analysis of drivers of migration in Tunisia

3.1 Environmental conditions

Country-level environment characteristics and challenges⁵

Major environmental threats in Tunisia are droughts and its effects on the population. Tunisia ranks 14th with absolute changes in land area affected by droughts and 15th for the absolute changes in the population exposed to droughts. Furthermore, during hot and dry summers parts of Tunisia are affected by recurrent fires.

Agricultural production is endangered by sea-level rise and variability in temperatures and precipitation, which may lead to decreased crop yields, increased water scarcity, reduced water quality, and changes in the growing seasons. The majority of Tunisia's agricultural production occurs in coastal zones, which are expected to experience significant sea-level rise by the end of the century. Since the 1980s one can observe very strong disparities according to the seasons as well as the interannual variability. The early 1980s are known for the succession of a number of dry years, which influences the general trend of the curves (Ministère des Affaires Locales et de l'Environnement and GEF, 2017, p. 18). Also higher temperatures can negatively impact crops by bringing about an increase in weeds and diseases. Increased temperature, sea-level rise, and decreased precipitation will also exacerbate existing water resources challenges, directly impacting the agricultural sector, which utilises approximately 80 per cent of the country's water supply.

In addition to drought, studies show Tunisia's susceptibility to flooding (Fig 8). It has been pointed out that areas in southern Tunisia are especially prone to these events due to its location on a low plane and its extremely erratic rainfall distribution. Though, even if it was not reason of internal displacement up to now it may become one in not so distant future.

Figure 8. Evolution of extreme precipitation events in mm

Source: Ministère des Affaires Locales et de l'Environnement and GEF, 2017, p. 19 after INM

⁵ This part was elaborated on the basis of an input given by FUME project members Jacob Schewe and Lucas Kluge

Floods and droughts are expected to occur more frequently in the coastal, desert, and urban areas (Fig. 9), which may result in crop losses, food insecurity and destruction of infrastructure. The increase in extreme precipitation events will cause an increase in the number of rapid disasters such as floods which cause internal displacement (Table 4). With the growing number and increasing strength of such disasters, one can expect that the numbers of internally displaced people will grow as well.

Figure 9. Evolution of precipitation (in %) by 2050 (A) and by 2100 (B) with the RCP 4.5 scenario

Source: Ministère des Affaires Locales et de l'Environnement and GEF, 2017, p. 21

Table 4. Disasters in Tunisia that caused internal displacement between 2017-2019

Source: <https://www.internal-displacement.org/countries/tunisia>

Region affected	Type of disaster	Date	Number of IDPs
Jendouba, Béja, Bizerte	Forest fires	2017-07-31	990
Nabeul	Storm	2018-09-22	3300
Manouba	Flood	2018-10-17	26
Bizerte	Flood	2018-08-24	42
Jerif	Flood	2019-02-06	20
Kasserine	Winter storm	2019-02-04	12

The annual probability of heatwaves in Tunisia is projected to increase from 1% to 19% between 2020 and 2099. Increase in temperatures is known to be a direct cause of death, especially in the elderly community who may suffer from strokes or heart attacks in extreme heat. A rise in temperature, and potential decreased water quantity and quality, can affect crop yields and contribute to food shortages and undernutrition, especially in children.

With its diverse natural environment, Tunisia relies heavily on the tourism industry, which comprises 6.5% of GDP and creates around 206,000 jobs. With 90% of tourist activity occurring along the coast, sea-level rise may lead to decreased water quality, a reduced number of beaches, and loss of coastal ecosystems.

The brief local-level environmental characteristic

For local-level characteristics were chosen five governorates located in three regions Kairouan and Kasserine (Centre-Ouest), Tunis (Northern-Est) and Monastir and Mahdia (Central-Est). From those five governorates, between 2009 and 2014, came to Sousse the biggest number of internal migrants.

The first and the main problem in all Tunisia and in those five governorates particularly, is overexploitation of water resources. Among others it is caused by an increase in the irrigated area dedicated to market gardening. In the Centre-West region irrigated market gardening is an agricultural activity providing employment to a largen umber of inhabitants of the region (135 days of work per hectare and per year). At the same time, it is there accompanied by poor water management and strong mobilisation of groundwater which can exceed 120%, the drop in the piezometric level and the quality of certain groundwater. The overexploitation of deep water tables and groundwater is accompanied by the multiplication of boreholes and deep wells dug illegally. The spectacular proliferation of surface wells is likely to cause, among other things, a maritime intrusion into groundwater, and thus make their waters excessively salty (Bounouh and Gsir, 2017, p. 63).

The second challenge, also typical for all Tunisia, is degradation of soil resources which is an effect of three main processes: water erosion, wind erosion and soil salinization. In the Centre-East region the degradation of natural vegetation, overgrazing, the uprooting of esparto and plowing downhill cause the watersheds of different wadis and water erosion. Not less important is insufficient maintenance of soil and water conservation projects. The Centre-West CIRADs estimate the area of land affected by erosion in this region at more than one million hectares, or more than half of the total area of useful agricultural land. The South-East region is struggling with desertification challenges. In many areas natural plant cover which constituted the protective factor of the soil against the wind action, was impaired during the early cultivation of the large rangelands, and further deteriorated by the vast olive-growing plantations. One of the areas at risk of desertification are Ouled Chemekh, Menzel Hached in Mahdia (Ministry of the Environment, GIZ 2012).

The erosive phenomenon, caused by natural factors, can be amply aggravated by human action: excessive and anarchic clearing of often fragile and marginal lands (case of the alfatière aquifer); excessive overgrazing of rangelands, brush, and natural woods; widespread dissemination of mechanisation in a sometimes inappropriate way (mechanised plowing of steeply sloping or fine-textured land; non-compliance with level-curve plowing; excessive use of disc plows altering the texture of the soil); growing substitution of worked fallows for grazed fallows (worked fallows leaves a good part of the soil bare and friable, thus exposing it for long months to both water and wind erosion) (Bounouh and Gsir, 2017). The phenomenon of salinization of agricultural soils can affect land cultivated in dry land, and especially land in irrigated areas. The study by the Ministry of Agriculture, reveals that this scourge of salinization of agricultural land is already dangerously affecting the irrigated areas of the Center-West, and more particularly the irrigated areas of the governorates of Kairouan and Sidi Bouzid because of the poor quality of irrigation water from shallow wells, and shallow water tables (Bounouh and Gsir, 2017, p. 63).

Finally, an important element that increases threats from the environment is poor management of waste collection and urbanisation. The significant number of public landfills are installed in sensitive sites such as sebkhas and wadis which have become dumps for household garbage, wastewater and vegetable waters. For instance in the governorate of Sfax, most of the landfills are uncontrolled, with effect of the solid waste deposited in the form of a terrace which further advances on the maritime public domain. On the other hand in the governorate of Mahdia, poor management of waste collection, together with an anarchic progression of urbanization in agricultural areas, exposes residents to several risks, in particular flooding (Bounouh and Gsir, 2017, p. 59).

The deterioration of agriculture conditions, if not managed and mitigated adequately, may cause deterioration of fields production, and in case of extreme difficult climate variability, may cause local population movements.

Such a situation in case of Syria, together with other factors pushed internal riots and what became one of triggers of Syrian War and further forced movements in that region (Gleick, 2014; Kelley et al., 2015).

Figure 10. Environmental threats and pressure on the natural environment in the region North-East
 Source: Bounouh and Gsir, 2017, p. 51, Ministre de l'équipement SDARNE, 2011. Ministre Environnement, ANPE
 GLZ, 2012. Conception: A. Bounouh, Cartographie: W. Bounouh

Figure 11. Environmental threats and pressure on the natural environment in the region Centr-East
 Source : Bounouh and Gsir, 2017, p. 58, Atlas cartographique Centre. Est SDARE Centre-est 2011 Tableau de bord l'environnement. Conception: A. Bounouh, Cartographie: W. Bounouh

Degradation of natural resources

- Over-exploitation of groundwater and deep waters
- Intensive farming in greenhouses
- Abusive exploitation of the wadis

Poorly controlled waste management

- Saturated landfill site
- Discharge of polluting waste (sebkha)
- Pollutant discharge (margine)
- Saturated wastewater treatment plants

Depletion of marine resources

- Overexploited fishing areas
- Regression of the seagrass meadow of Posidonia
- polluting deposits (phosphogypsum)

Degradation of sensitive environments

- Coastal erosion
- Accelerated sea level rise
- Beginning of the desertification process
- Silting and appearance of mobile dunes
- Salinisation and sea waterlogging

Strong pressure on the space

- Extension of anarchic settlements
- Concentration of industrial units
- Anarchic urbanisation

Figure 12. Environmental threats and pressure on the natural environment in the region Centre-West
 Source: Bounouh and Gsir, 2017, p. 64, Atlas cartographique SDARE Centre-ouest Tableau de bord de l'environnement, GIZ.2012 Conception: A. Bounouh, Cartographie: W. Bounouh

3.2 Demographic situation

Tunisia had 11 708 370 inhabitants on January 2020, of which 50.2% were women. As Tunisia has undergone its demographic transition, the average annual growth rate of the population is increasingly slow and stands at 1.03% over the period 2004-2014 (from 2.35% over 1984-1994 to 1.21% over the period 1994-2004). Life expectancy at birth is on average 75.1 years. It is 74.5 years for men and 77.8 years for women (Ministère des Affaires Locales et de l'Environnement and GEF, 2017, p. 10).

The Tunisian population is starting to age slightly. In just over a decade (2009-2019), the age group of the elderly (65 and over) has increased from 7.5 to 8.6% of the total population. The weight of the active population (15-64 years) fell from 69 to 67.2%. The revolution seems to have given Tunisians enthusiasm to have more babies, since after a cycle of declining child population rates before 2011, births have started to rise again, pushing the rate of the age 0-14 years from 23.27% in 2011 to 24.2% in 2019% (Plecher, 2020).

This social profile influences the average migration age. The average age of internal migrants between 2009 and 2014 reached 26.2 years against 24.7 years for migrants between 1987 and 1994. The majority of migrants are between 20 and 40 years old i.e. 223 379 out of 430 000 migrants. This age group represents 51.9% of total migrants between governorates. The highest number of migrants (67,514 people) is observed in the age group (25-29 years). Beyond the age of 40, the number of migrants per age group decreases as one advances in age (tables 5 and 6).

Table 5. Share of different age groups among migrants

Source: INS, RGPH. 2015

Ages groups	0-14	15-19	20-24	25-29	30-34	35-39	40-44	45-49	50-54	55-59	60 & +	Total
Number	7 930	2 119	6 400	6 215	4 770	3 026	1 909	1 307	1 003	738	1 079	36 496
%	21,7	5,8	17,5	17,0	13,1	8,3	5,2	3,6	2,7	2,0	3,0	100,0

Table 6. Share of different age groups among migrants (%)

Source: INS, RGPH. 2015

Ages groups	0-14	15-45	< 45	Total
%	21,7	67,0	11,3	100,0

Table 7. Number of migrants and Male rate divided for age groups

Source: INS, General Population and Housing Census. 2014. Vol.5. Migration characteristics

Ages groups	Number of migrants	Masculinity rate
15-19	20 650	1 096
20-24	57 053	905
25-29	67 514	616
30-34	60 144	833
35-39	38 668	1 158
40-44	24 366	1 338
45-49	17 349	1 304

For Sousse governorate, 2/3 of the migrants to Sousse are 15-45 years old (Table 7). The Tunisian migration is mostly internal and dominated by male youth usually from rural to urban areas (Amara, Ayadi and Jemmali, 2018). This characteristic is changing in time and with regard to internal and international migration. During the period of 1987-1994 the sex ratio, with a maximum of 1 201 men per 1000 women recorded, was to the advantage of men. Since then, however, the trend has shifted and reached even the level of 962 men for 1,000

women between 2009-2014. Especially in the younger age groups the sex ratio (the number of men per 1000 women) is low and in the 20-24 age group it amounts to 905, 616 in the 25-29 age group and 833 in the 30-34 age group. It is mostly due to the more massive immigration of young girls who came to work in the big cities as workers or as housekeepers. In the age group over 35 years old, the sex ratio is again dominated by men Table 7 (Bounouh and Gsir, 2017, p. 39). Worth to remember is the fact that as far as for internal migration the women have overcome men, for international migration men are still a large majority.

3.3 Sociocultural context

Education

The Tunisian education system is divided into following stages: 1) basic education (compulsory from the age of 6 until the age of 16) which composes of a) primary and b) general or vocational education, 2) three-year secondary education, and 3) tertiary education which since 2006 is based on the 'LMD' system (licence, master, doctorate) (Flayols, Jongerius and de Bel-Air, 2019, p. 1).

The Tunisian education system was reformed in the late 1980s. Ben Ali's regime, under which the reform was implemented, aimed to improve in terms of international rankings and official development goals such as alphabetization, school enrolment and gender equity. The reform made school compulsory until the age of 16 and created the vocational training curriculum. It also improved access to education (Schaefer, 2018, p. 58). Tunisia has relied on education for its development, now devoting around 6% of its GDP to it. The illiteracy rate has fallen sharply since independence (Ministère des Affaires Locales et de l'Environnement and GEF, 2017, p. 9). However, although more children were enrolled in the school system it did not adequately affect the increase in the level of education. The drop out of school remained high, especially within secondary education. Another issue is the limited creative ability and advanced knowledge skills of students which was indicated with regard to Tunisian's students by the Arab Knowledge Report. The report also highlighted the fact that many youths continue to obtain an education that does not reflect the needs of labour markets (UNDP, 2016).

The position of education in the centre of political agenda during the reign of Habib Bourguiba created anticipation among the society that education automatically allows for social mobility and success. Until the 1980s, most of the graduates were absorbed by the large public sector. However, the "massification" of higher education led to a huge number of graduates in certain sectors, the downgrading of education quality and lack of job-seekers in non-academic and not in public sector professions (Schaefer, 2018). Over-educated young people coming back to their less developed regions of origin, dominated by agriculture sector, are not willing to work in agriculture any more (Sobczak-Szelc and Fekih, 2020). Therefore university graduates and graduates of vocational training have the highest unemployment rates and the longest unemployment lapses. On average it is two years and four months, which is nine times more than non-graduates. Those who decide not to wait for a job in the public sector, decide to work in a private one, which often offers work below the qualifications, low paid and with poor working conditions. Therefore the mismatch in Tunisia consists of both over-education and under-education as they are missing specific skills such as the newest technological skills, language, and soft skills (Schaefer, 2018, p. 64).

All these factors push young students and graduates to look for possibilities to search for studying or work options abroad. As a result, the level of education is relatively high among migrants. 73.2% have a secondary or higher level of education, while the same rate does not exceed 48.6% for the total population. The proportion of graduates among Tunisian migrants in OECD countries is over 25 %. Similar percentage constituted those who have completed tertiary education among young migrants (25-29 years). However, among young Tunisians reaching North America, this exceeds 70 % (UNDP, 2016, p. 259). After returning, the situation of graduates changes slightly. According to research by David and Nordman (2017), the share of jobs matching the education among return migrants was 66.2%. Over education was at the level of 12.2% and was higher among non-migrants where it was 14.4%.6

The illiteracy rate is lower among younger generations in comparison with other groups. Also the general illiteracy rate among migrants is low (8.9%) compared to the general rate of 19.3% in 2014. This can be explained by the young age of migrants who have benefited from the generalisation and free public education, both in rural and urban areas. The illiteracy rate varies, however, according to gender and the governorate of exit. The rate is slightly higher (11-13%) among migrants leaving the governorates from the interior. It is even higher among young women leaving the same governorates (12-15%).

3.4 Economic context

One of the indicators on which analysts and researchers rely to understand the root causes of internal and outmigration is the Regional Development Indicator (RDI) of each Tunisian governorate. The acute gaps between these regional indicators (Table 8) as well as the destination of migration flows and the volume of migration deficits or surpluses, in each of the governorates, are indicative of the territorial divide in Tunisia, between prosperous coastal and urban areas and sluggish and declining inland and rural regions.

Table 8. Regional Development Index in regions of Tunisian in 2018

Source: Institut Tunisien de la Compétitivité et des Études Quantitatives. 2019. *L'Indicateur de Développement Régional (IDR), comme guide pour la conception d'une nouvelle carte du développement* (p. 25).

Governorates	Economic regions	Regional Development Index
Tunis	District of (Great) Tunis	0,531- 0,593
Ariana		
Ben Arous		
Nabeul		
Sousse		
Monastir	Eastern North/North-East	0,484 – 0,520
Manouba	District of Tunis	
Bizerte	North East	
Zaghouan	Centre-East	
Sfax	South-East	
Gabès	North-West	0,452 – 0,483
Medenine		
Kef		
Siliana		
Mahdia		
Gafsa	South-West	0,388 – 0,449
Kebili		
Tozeur		
Jendouba	North-West	
Bejà	Centre-West	
Kairouan		
Sidi bouzid		
Kasserine		
Tataouine	South-East	

The amplification of the negative migratory balance for instance from the Centre-West region, is explained by the scarcity of employment opportunities, especially for higher education graduates in increasing numbers. In this region, there are only 288 industrial companies which employ a workforce greater than or equal to 10 jobs, which represents only 5.3% of the total number of companies nationwide. The number of fully exporting companies is low (72 companies) which represents only 3% of the total. The modesty of the industrial fabric of the Center-West is threatened by the invasion of the local market by foreign products at low prices, the

degradation of the industrial infrastructure, due to the lack of consolidation, maintenance, renewal, and modernization of basic infrastructure in industrial areas (road network, electricity network, and sewerage network).

The municipal population assimilated to the urban environment is still low in the Center-West region. In fact, the percentage of the population living in urban areas in the entire region represents 6.8% of the entire population of Tunisia. In 2014, the urbanization rate was only 27.1% in the governorate of Sidi Bouzid against 43.6 and 35.3% respectively in the governorates of Kasserine and Kairouan. Despite the weakness of urbanization, the Center-West region experiences shortcomings in urban planning, particularly in the administrative centers of the governorates of Kairouan, Kasserine and Sidi Bouzid. These failings are manifested by the proliferation of anarchic constructions and a certain explosion of urbanization. Environmental services are deficient in these districts (roads, sanitation, rainwater drainage). This situation increased especially after January 14, 2011, with the proliferation of illegal dumps and the discharge of wastewater into the natural environment (Ministry of Equipment SDARECO, 2009).

During the 2011-2020 decade, Tunisia faced an unprecedented economic and social crisis where all economic and social indicators were red or orange. The levels of these indicators have not been so bad since 2011. This situation has worsened with the crisis of the COVID-19 pandemic. The unemployment rate rose to a peak of 18% in 2020, against 14.8% in 2014 (INS 2017b, 174p) (Tab. 11). Almost 800,000 people were unemployed in 2020, compared with an average of 600,000 to 650,000 before 2020. Graduates were the most affected (30.2%), graduated women even more (50%) (BCT, 2021).

According to an extended analysis of the Arab Mediterranean countries (AMCs) labour markets, one of the main problems is the mismatch between the outcomes of the educational system and the qualifications required on the job market (Fargues, and Iván 2010). One of the highlighted causes was the high prevalence of employment in the public sector until the 1980s that led the universities to orient their training offer towards humanities and social sciences. The result is a high concentration of graduates in fields for which labour demand barely increased in the last decades (Barguelli and Zaiem, 2013).

Table 9. Employed population in City of Sousse compared to the governorate and national level, per main economic activities sectors, in 2014

Source: INS. GPHC. 2017. Sousse Volume.

Administrative Unit	Sousse Municipal District	Employed Population	Main activities sectors (%)					Unemployed (%)
			Agriculture & fishing	Industry/ Manufacturing	Services	Not reported	Total %	
Municipality of Sousse	Sousse Medina	12 313	0,8	16	82,9	0,3	100	9,5
	Sousse Riadh	23 110	0,5	38,6	60,7	0,2	100	14,0
	Sousse Jawhara	31 009	0,5	23	76,2	0,3	100	10,2
	Sousse Sidi Abdelhamid	18 249	1,3	43,1	55,4	0,2	100	15,0
Total Governorate		224 730	3,1	39,8	56,9	0,2	100	11,5
Total Tunisia		3 295 965	10,5	34,5	54,9	0,2	100	14,82

Regional development and the Tunisian internal migration

One can observe variation regarding migration rates across governorates (David and Marouani, 2017, p. 4). In the decade following Tunisia's independence in 1956, the political and economic weight of the capital and the "tunisification" of the administration (departure of French civil servants, replaced by the Tunisian elite of

the time) made Tunis the only pole with a surplus, while all the other regions recorded a migration deficit and lost their populations for the benefit of the capital. (cf. net migration in 1966). From the 1970s and until 2010, the migration map of Tunisia was divided between two trends which lasted more than 50 years (1960-2014):

1) A global and continual deficit of the inland regions which recorded or maintained their net negative migration (such as the North-West: governorates of Jendouba, Beja, Kef and Siliana) or suffered from a continuous deepening and aggravation of their migratory deficit. These deficits doubled or tripled from one decade to the next one, from the 1970s to 2010;

2) Coastal and urban regions maintained their surplus and have continued, for 5 decades, to strengthen their attractive power and their capacities to polarise populations, public and private facilities and services. They also strengthen their control of command functions and activities that create wealth and employment (industry, tourism, wholesale and luxury trade, banks...). 80% of industrial employment and almost all exporting industries are located on the coast and in the big cities. The same applies to public equipment and infrastructure (highways, airports, railway lines... etc.). The results converge towards a concentration of [national] GDP in certain "rich" governorates with a high population density. The concentration of wealth and the inequality of distribution of GDP per governorate does not change since the second half of the last century.

Regarding the development indexes, the inter-regional development gaps have not been corrected since independence (Meddeb, 2020). The Tunisian administration and authorities did not publish accurate regional data before the 2011 uprising. Since that time the inter-regional gaps and local development have become burning issues in the public debate. Already in 2012, a Ministry of Regional Development was created to address this issue. Data on regional development indicators (IDR/RDI) were successively published in 2013 and in 2019 by the Tunisian Institute of Competitiveness and Quantitative Studies (ITCEQ). The differences (gaps) in the Synthetic Regional Development Indexes (SRDIs) support this interpretation and clearly demonstrate the widening development gap between the coast, on the one hand, and the interior and the South, on the other. If we take the two extremes in consideration, we will have the following: the SRDI of Tunis (0.76) was almost 6 times higher than that of Kasserine (0.16). The Regional Development Indicators (RDIs) of the coastal regions were double those of the inland and southern areas (Fig. 13). In 2000, 12.5% of the wealth was generated in the governorate of Tunis, 10.3% in the governorate of Nabeul and 11.2% in the governorate of Sousse, while the share of the governorate of Tataouine is only about 0.5% of the national wealth (ITCEQ, 2012). Almost 3/4 (73.2%) of the wealth and added value are produced on the North-East coast of the country's map (District of Tunis, North-East and Centre-East) and gather almost 62% of Tunisian population, whereas the remaining 3/4 of the country (North-West; Centre-West, South-East and South-West) contribute only 26.8% of the country's wealth (INS, 2021). In other words, seven coastal governorates (Greater Tunis and Centre-East) have SRDIs above 0.55, while all the others are below this level, and seven other governorates in the North-West and South-West are below 0.40%.

Figure 13. Synthetic Index of Regional Development of Tunisian Governorates in 2012
 Source: Tunisian Institute of Competitiveness and Quantitative Studies, 2012 p. 8-9

In 2021, the National Institute of Statistics (INS) published the results of a study on the contribution of the Tunisian regions to the production of national wealth in 2016. These results confirm the same trends as those recorded by the ITCEQ (Tab 12) (ITCEQ, 2018).

Table 10: Shares of regions in GDP, Population and Poverty rates

Sources: (*) : INS, 2021; (**) : INS, 2015; (***) : National Survey on the Budget, Consumption and the Standard of Living of Households. 2015.

Regions	Share in national GDP in 2016 in % *	Share in total population in 2014 in % **	Poverty rate in 2015 in % ***
District of Tunis	35,9	24,1	5,3
North-East	13,5	14,0	11,6
North-West	7,2	10,7	28,4
Centre-East	23,8	23,6	11,4
Centre-West	7,3	13,1	30,8
South-East	7,8	9,1	18,5
South-West	4,5	5,5	17,5
Total	100,0	100,0	15,2

Thus, the GDP/capita of Greater Tunis (11,780 TND) is 2.5 times higher than that of the Central West (4,472 TND). Only two coastal regions (Greater Tunis and the Centre-East) exceed the average GDP/capita (7,943 TND), while all the other inland regions (the North-East, in the West and the South) have GDPs below the average. The Greater Tunis region accounts for 35.9% of national wealth production (Fig 14), while its population represents only 24.4% of the total population of Tunisia (Fig 15). The contribution of the Centre West to the national GDP does not exceed 7.3% against 12.9% of the total population.

Figure 14. Regional contribution to the wealth production (INS 2021)

Figure 14. Regional contribution to the wealth production (INS 2021)

Only two coastal regions (Greater Tunis and the Centre East) exceed the average GDP/capita (7 943 TND), while all the other regions in the interior (the North-East, the West and the South) have GDPs below the average (Fig 16).

Figure 16. GDP/capita/region

Source: INS, 2021

We can go further in cross-referencing development indicators which show that the inland regions, located in the West of the country, especially the North-West and the Centre-West, have high poverty rates, double the national average, and low shares in the national GDP (Table 10). The share of the Greater Tunis in the GDP is 12 points higher (36%) than its share in the country's population (24%). This ratio is reversed for the Centre-West (7.3% of GDP against 13.1% of the country's population).

Table 7. Number of migrants and Male rate divided for age groups

Source: INS, General Population and Housing Census. 2014. Vol.5. Migration characteristics

Governorates	Regional belonging	Tunisia: Evolution of Net Internal Migration (Difference between arrivals and leavings) between 1961 and 2014 (Source: INS, GPHCs)					
		1961-1966	1969 - 1975	1979 - 1984	1989 - 1994	1999 - 2004	2009-2014
Interior and Southern Governorates							
Zaghuan	North East	-	-3000	-1300	-1591	-785	-900
Béja	North West	-34495	-10700	-10300	-7037	-9601	-7600
Jendouba		-19329	-7900	-8200	-9432	-9936	-12100
ElKef		-32605	-7700	-8900	-10286	-11155	-7000
Siliana		-	-5600	-9200	-9141	-11692	-8300
Kairouan	Center-West	-9291	-3400	-6200	-11519	-22984	-19400
Kasserine		-6107	-1500	-4400	-6918	-16923	-12400
Sidi Bouzid		-	1500	-1900	-5493	-14085	-7500
Gabes	South East	-15896	-800	200	-3163	-2367	-1300
Medenine		-25315	2500	1500	1502	2696	3500
Tataouine		-	-	-100	-1071	-2455	-2000
Gafsa	South West	-4957	-2500	-1700	-5625	-7783	-5100
Tozeur		-	-	1000	1012	-586	100
Kebilli		-	-	400	1018	-1716	-700
Coastal Governorates							
Tunis	Tunis District	202316	40100	-37600	-21750	-27210	-28700
Ariana		-	-	53700	34572	37902	41200
Ben Arous		-	-	29300	34972	36942	25100
Manouba		-	-	-	-	9722	8800

Nabeul	North East	-2986	500	1400	5025	7055	10800
Bizerte		-8611	-7800	-6500	-3719	-2823	-5300
Sousse	Center East	-35097	300	5800	8232	21863	15100
Monastir		-	5900	3300	5030	16954	11800
Mahdia		-	2200	-900	-2069	-2452	-1800
Sfax		-7627	-2200	600	7452	11392	3900

	Interior and Southern Governorates
	Coastal Governorates
-	Governorates not yet created at the date of the concerned Census

3.5 Sousse: Urban Fracture

As a coastal and a relatively big town, the City of Sousse is well privileged and its population benefits from a good level of public equipment and basic infrastructures (sewerage system, drinking water, natural gas, and power (electricity)). Households have also a high level of home facilities (Table 12).

Table 12. City of Sousse: % of housing benefiting from public equipment and infrastructure networks (sewerage system, Drinking water, Natural gas and power; % of houses with facilities and the number of houses without facilities), in 2014

Source : INS. RGPH. 2014. Sousse Volume.

Delegation	Public Systems of				% of houses with			Number of houses without		
	Sewerage system	Drinking water	Natural gas	Power	Kitchen	Toilets	Bathroom/ shower	Kitchen	Toilets	Bathroom/ shower
Sousse Medina	98,25	95,27	48,24	98,03	99,13	99,64	97,63	132	55	359
Sousse Riadh	95,96	616	47,67	98,31	98,96	99,31	96,22	215	143	784
Sousse Jawhara	97,41	833	63,89	98,96	99,31	99,66	98,10	205	102	565
Sousse Sidi Abdelhamid	96,15	1 158	49,71	98,14	98,28	99,07	90,70	261	141	1 412
Total of Governorate	91,81	1 338	49,35	98,33	98,28	98,81	94,68	3 156	2 181	9 731
Total of Tunisia	82,26	1 304	30,27	97,66	97,95	97,98	90,42	47 864	47 213	224 125

Nonetheless, the city of Sousse suffers from a socio-spatial fracture between the poor or low-income populations who live in the spontaneous (or informal, or unregulated) housing areas, mostly located south of the city centre, and the middle-class or well-off populations who occupy the neighbourhoods located west and north of the city centre. This social divide inevitably results in an urban fracture which poses problems for the social cohesion of the city. More than 20 informal settlements called "cities" are concerned.

These informal cities are located in the areas of Sousse where the natural and social environment is degraded (not enough clean drinkable water resources, high level of criminality, lack of employment possibilities). These are destinations of internal migrations and at the same time main source of undocumented international migrants. The inhabitants of the southern neighbourhoods are mostly from the rural areas around Sousse or the interior regions in the centre-west. These illegally inhabited areas are devoid of sewage systems – it either does not exist or is not adequate and not renovated. Additionally, in the area of southern Sousse some companies and factories drain industrial used water to dry riverbeds and cause degradation of the environment, especially alluvial water resources. This contributes to the filling of marginalisation among inhabitants of those poor areas and make the willingness of departure even stronger.

In a document entitled "Development Strategy of the City of Sousse" (SDVS, 2013 p. 59), the Municipal Council of the City of Sousse considered that this socio-spatial divide is a risk to the cohesion of the city and especially to the populations living in these neighbourhoods because of the various inequalities resulting from this situation:

- The intensification of internal migratory flows towards the city has been accompanied by a spectacular multiplication of spontaneous housing suburbs, which has made it difficult to meet the needs of their inhabitants for basic urban facilities (road and sewerage networks), basic public services (schools, urban transport, hospital units), unhealthy or poorly equipped housing, etc.
- A degraded environment due to the weakness or absence of sanitation networks, factory discharges and pollution of groundwater tables.
- High rates of unemployment, underemployment and precarious work, especially among young people in the suburbs.

These forms of socio-spatial marginality are considered to be factors that contribute to preparing the ground for migration projects abroad.

3.6 Political context - revolution in Tunisia

The current social and economic crisis is exacerbated by a political crisis due to governmental and institutional instability (more than 11 governments in 10 years). The crisis of confidence between the political elites and the population. A large part of the Tunisian population considers that the 2011 revolution is far from having met their hopes and expectations in terms of economic development, transparency and good governance, or social equality and equity between regions and territories.

The 10th anniversary (14 January 2021) of the 2011's Tunisian Uprising has been marked by night-time protests and violent clashes with the security forces. These demonstrations were conducted by young people from the poor and 'working classes' neighbourhoods of many coastal Tunisian cities (Tunis, Monastir, Sousse and others) or from the interior (Siliana, Kasserine...) (Boubakri, 2021). The violent demonstrations of 2021, like other social movements that occurred during the previous anniversaries of the revolt, reflect the population's frustration with the continuous deterioration of all socio-economic indicators.

The political situation has deteriorated further since 25 July 2021, when the President of the Republic, Kaies Saied, merged the government and parliament, and then concentrated executive and legislative powers in his own hands. These measures have been strongly contested by the opposition (in particular Ennahda Party) and criticised by some of Tunisia's key international partners (USA, EU).

The health crisis linked to Covid 19 has aggravated the socio-economic situation in the country, particularly overexposing vulnerable populations to the pandemic and to the loss of income and employment caused by the preventive measures against the virus. The spread of the pandemic, since March 2020, has weighed heavily on the activity of many sectors, such as export-oriented manufacturing industries, which have been strongly affected by the slowdown in industry worldwide, particularly in Tunisia's main trading partners in the Euro zone. The impact has also affected the sectors oriented towards the local market such as the building industry, as well as market services (transport, tourism, and gastronomy sectors). In addition, the deterioration of the social climate, the claims and the blocking of production sites have weighed on the activity of the extractive industries, particularly the energy and phosphate and their derivatives sectors. All these influenced the economy, especially the unemployment rate. In other words, there has been a continuous and widespread trend of deterioration and weakening of these indicators. Among these indicators we can mention:

- A continuous decline in the rate of GNP growth and its maintenance at a very low level. In 2020, following the impact of the health crisis, a historic contraction (-8.8% compared to 0.9% in 2019) was registered (BCT, 2021).
- The weakness and the fall of investments: from more than 25% of GDP in 2010 to less than 20% in 2016 and... 13,3% in 2020 (BCT, 2021).
- The widening of public deficits, following the explosion of the debt that reached 84.3 of GDP in 2020, against 72.5 in 2019. In 2021 Tunisia had to repay TND 8.3 billion, i.e. an increase of 42.5% compared to the amount repaid in 2020 (BCT, 2021).
- The depreciation of the value of the Tunisian Dinar against the main currencies (such as US\$ and Euro).
- The degradation of the purchasing power of the middle class and even more of the working classes. General Consumer Price Index increases reached from 3% in 2011 to 7,5% in 2018, and 6,7% in 2019 (INS & OECD, 2018 & BCT, 2021).
- The deterioration in the quality of public services (health, education, transport, etc.), equipment and basic infrastructure.

A political reading of the migration map of recent decades shows that regions that revolted in 2008 (the Gafsa region) and in December 2010 - January 2011 (Sidi Bouzid and Kasserine), and which were at the origin of the revolutionary process of 2011, are the regions of the interior and the South which have registered the highest migration deficits over the last five decades. Cities however, do not deliver substantial solutions. Therefore, internal migration, which is fragile to this general context of crisis, disenchantment and frustration, continues with the explosion of irregular migration and the draining of skills. Thus, we can consider that irregular migration of Tunisians (most of them are young people) is one of the most significant and symbolic message of protest and of anger addressed to the authorities, to the politics and to the whole society.

3.7 The impact of migration policies on internal international mobility

Tunisians have migrated in large numbers towards Europe since the mid-twentieth century. This migration has been mostly economically driven and some of the most popular destinations was France, the former coloniser. In the mid-1970s additionally Libya and later in 1980s Italy became the main destinations of labour migration. Due to the proximity of Libya, the migrations to this country had mostly circular character. After the oil crisis in 1973-74, and later when the European governments introduced new visa requirements and increased immigration controls, family migration became the main legal entry pathway towards the EU. Many others decided for overstaying or irregular entry (Natter, 2015). During the Ben Ali regime the control of irregular migration by Tunisian authorities was treated as a bargaining factor, and increased or decreased at strategic moments to enable the country to make new deals with European, mostly Italian, policymakers (Lixi, 2018).

In fact, Tunisia, like other transit migration's third countries, is trapped by the EU and its member States' pressures in order to externalise the EU's borders controls towards its nationals to keep them as far away as possible from the EU's external borders. Despite the historical traditions of regional cooperation (i.e Arab Maghreb Union) or interregional cooperation (ECOWAS member countries for example), Tunisian authorities apply strict restrictions towards Sub-Saharan country nationals (Boubakri, 2021b).

After the fall of the Ben Ali regime, the number of Tunisian irregular migrants trying to reach Italian coasts in 2011 exceeded 23.000 people. Soon after the new government was settled and border controls were introduced again, those numbers decreased significantly just till 2020 when another pic was observed (see the section on **Irregular emigration from Tunisia, above**).

Tunisia, after having signed⁶ or renewed readmission agreements since the late 1990s until 2020, saw the number of its deported nationals jumping to 33 945 Tunisians over nine years (2011-2019), representing 28.6% of the 118 845 Maghrebi expelled by the EU members States during this period (including 58 168 Moroccans and 26 741 Algerians) (Frontex, 2010-2020).

But Tunisian authorities try to avoid these pressures. They are, for example, more vigilant and are not in a hurry to conclude the negotiations for the signing of the Mobility Partnership protocols. Tunisia refuses the readmission of others than its own citizens, mainly nationals of Sub-Saharan countries. It is negotiating with the EU and its member states to extend visa facilitation to new professional categories and to increase the number of long-term study or economic visas (for job search and fixed-term employment) (Boubakri, 2021b).⁷

⁶ Four agreements were signed or updated with Italy between 1998 and 2011, one agreement was signed with France in 2008, two other ones with Norway and Switzerland in 2012

⁷ F On migration and the labour market in Tunisia, you can consult the country fiche:

ETF SKILLS AND MIGRATION COUNTRY FICHE TUNISIA

https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2021-11/etf_skills_and_migration_country_fiche_tunisia_2021_en_1.pdf

4. Results

4.1. Who moves: profile

"When you grow up in these difficult situations, you can't ask for more. You know what your family can afford. Your father cannot provide you with more."

(TunMig19)

The majority of the interviewees come from the governorate of Kairouan, or, more precisely, its rural areas (Al-Alaa, Sidi Amor Bouhajla, Ousletia etc.). These areas are known for their agriculture, but they also suffer from economic and social marginalisation, high unemployment and poverty rates, low development index, deteriorating infrastructure and environmental crises, in particular difficult access to water which makes the practice of agriculture a choice that requires substantial financial investment. The sample also includes participants from other regions: in the South, such as Tataouin, Gabes and Kebili, and in the North West, such as Beja and El Kef. A few came from coastal cities such as Mehdia and Monastir. Migrants from coastal areas find it less difficult to settle than others, especially those from the interior. As mentioned in the introductory part of the report, for a long time Tunisia had a distinction between the interior regions and the coastal region, the latter enjoying not only economic, but also political influence. The country's first two presidents were, respectively, from the cities of Monastir and Sousse. In the 2011 uprising, equality and positive discrimination in favour of disadvantaged regions were among the demands of the protesters.

Regarding family structure, most of the respondents came from families with four or more siblings. In the interviews, what was often mentioned, was a situation in which it was the father who was responsible for earning money, being the so-called 'breadwinner', and the one who eventually made the first migration, often abroad, to earn a living. Indeed, many of the people we spoke to had closer or more distant relatives already settled abroad, which was also mentioned by one of the interviewees in our sample: *'We also have people who migrated abroad, especially to France' (TunMig20).*

In order to give relief and support to the family, they were often pressured to find some work which would provide additional income for the household. Such a situation was mentioned by many, including a newly arrived male migrant, who declared:

We are 8 in the family, 6 siblings and my parents. My father was the breadwinner when we were at school. When we grew up, every one of us got a job and we relied on ourselves. We are financially independent now. My father was the only breadwinner as a daily worker. You cannot ask for more than what they have. (...) Psychologically, I wanted to study to escape these conditions or to change them. (TunMig19)

The majority of our interviewees received higher education (14 respondents), 7 obtained their Baccalaureate, a further three dropped out during secondary school and another three after the primary level of education. It can be observed that within the interviewed sample settled migrants are both older and less educated, newcomers are usually younger and better educated (they often hold university degrees or are students); also education was often cited as the justification of the second group for coming to Sousse.

4.2. Migration decision-making

'There are no opportunities available there' - economic reasons

"I loved my region, but I left it because it is marginalised and has no job opportunities"

In general, what makes people move are 'circumstances and the scarcity of jobs. [They are] *obliged to get a job*. [And are] *looking for a source of income*' (TunMig22). Challenges related to finding a job were mentioned by all groups of interviewees as the most important factor influencing the decision to migrate: '*Because there are no job opportunities*' (TunMig01) or '*The place where [they] live is rural and doesn't offer jobs*' (TunMig25). Agriculture was mentioned as the main opportunity available for young people in almost all regions of origin:

"(...) the only area available is agriculture. If you inherit land and have financial resources, you can cultivate your land. Otherwise, you need to move to Sfax, Tunis, or Sousse, but in Hajeb Al Ayoun it is not possible. It is a town surrounded by several rural areas where the only working domain is agriculture. If you have capital, you can work. If you don't, you should move to a different area. Almost 90% of young people finish their secondary education in Hajeb Al Ayoun, if they dropped out, they would end up working in construction or factories in Sousse, Sfax, or Tunis, i.e. big cities."

(TunMig19)

"You must rely on yourself. No one will provide you with anything. The least the government can do is [give you] a farmer certificate so you can get a truck. People of my age all have trucks there."

(TunMig17)

In other, more industrialised, regions the possibilities of work in the industry are also limited. One example shows a situation in the region of Gafsa, from which three of our respondents came. The interviewee, an elderly lady, complained that 'at the Phosphate Company of Gafsa (CPG): *"(...) those who have the right to work there, are either from other regions or use one's connections. Thus, youth from the region are obliged to work outside of it. For instance, they move to the region of Sousse to work in factories because [in Gafsa there are] one or two sewing factories. (...) we do not have many factories which urge people to move to other regions"*' (TunMig01). Such a situation was also commonly known by newcomers, one of whom explained in more detail:

"The region where I grew up is rich in terms of phosphate, but it is marginalised. It lacks any job opportunities (...). Even if I had a degree and I was looking for a job, I would not get a good salary. The salary at call centres is bad, it is 200 dinars (60 euros). There are factories there when I was a student, I worked in a factory. I loved my region, but I left it because it is marginalised and has no job opportunities."

(TunMig08)

Similar opinions could be heard also with regards to other regions such as Ain Drhahem: 'Everyone will tell you that Ain Drahem is beautiful but there are no job opportunities. If people could find jobs, they would not need to leave', explained one of the interviewees (TunMig10). This problem is difficult, especially for the new generation of well-educated youth. The phrase 'There are no stable job opportunities' was repeated like a mantra by different interviewees.

"Students graduate as teachers or in other disciplines and stay jobless because there are no job opportunities. (...) There are no factories and that is why people who study no longer want to go back there."

(TunMig12)

"There are no stable job opportunities. All of my friends work either in the army, the civil defence or, the police department, as either a sergeant or prefect. They drop out of school at the high school level (3rd year or Bac) and become a prefect."

(TunMig05)

"(...) there are not so many job opportunities. Neither of my friends works in El Oueslatia. They are either working in the army or in the police department. They cannot all work in a high school, a municipality or the administration. Even if they were teachers, they could not be hired in the same school. They end up looking for jobs in Sousse, Tunis or Hammamet."

(TunMigo5)

"I decided to get a job, I told my father that I wanted to work and that I looked in Gafsa but couldn't find a job. I worked in a copy centre in Gafsa. Back then, I earned 100 dinars (30 euros). I worked from 8 am to 4 pm. I looked for another job but couldn't find one. If I found a job, I wouldn't leave. I can speak French, I looked on the Internet but didn't find any jobs. When I first moved, I came not to Sousse but to Monastir."

(TunMigo8)

It needs to be stressed, however, that young people often do not want work which they are overqualified for, i.e. which is 'below' their education, competencies and ambitions. It can take even a few years for them to find a job, after they graduate, irrespective of the type of education.

An interviewee from Gabes explained:

"My sister finished studying and took the nurse examination when it was not done through orientation. She was jobless for a year then she got a job offer. My other sister is a caregiver. She was jobless for 3 years then got a job."

(TuMigo4)

Not without significance is the cultural change visible in the generation of youth who are willing to find new opportunities for themselves. Often, they want to have an income fast, without waiting for the harvest, which is when jobs in agriculture become available. When youth cannot find opportunities for quick income, they look for it in other regions. Although this happened in the past - as exemplified by the story of a man who did not want to wait to fix a tooth until his father sold a cow - in recent years it has become more common.

"I was in love with a girl and came because of her. I had a broken tooth and I asked mom to tell my father to give me money to fix it. He told her that he needed to wait until he sold the cow. Was I supposed to wait until he did so? My mother (may she rest in peace) gave me 5 dinars (1.50 euros) to get to Sousse."

(TunMig15)

The income in rural areas of origin is very low. 'A daily worker (...) earned TND 8 or 9'. And there is always a risk as 'sometimes he gets the money, sometimes he gets fired' (TunMigo3). In construction 'you have to work for 20 days but you need to wait for a month to get paid and you only earn 80 or 90 dinars (24 euros) [per day]' (TunMig22). Another interviewee admitted that 'salary at call centres is [also] bad, it is 200 dinars (60 euros)' (TunMigo8). Some interviewees underlined that they prefer to 'work and earn 10 and not ask anyone for anything' (TunMig16), or that 'the salary is low, but it is better than staying unemployed. Getting paid 100 dinars is better than borrowing money from other people' (TunMig21), they 'would rather be tired but not need anything' (TunMig16). Finally, they admitted that they left because they 'don't want to stay jobless. In the countryside, you can work for one day and stay jobless for the remaining days' (TunMig21). However, other interviewees indicated that many young people do not want to work for a very low income, they stay unemployed 'and their condition is terrible. (...) They don't want to work and earn 15 or 20 dinars per day. They got used to it' (TunMig16). One person told the story of another interviewee who said of his youth:

"I went home and stayed in Mjez el Beb for a year. I didn't have a job, so I stayed at the café. I did not have any responsibilities. A relative told me: you are staying here without a job. I didn't want to get a job, I see myself in a better place. This is a small country and to work in a factory is nothing."

(TunMig11)

In general, the need to improve one's economic situation often results from wanting to meet social needs

either of the individual, such as getting married or becoming independent from the family, or of the household. As one interviewee explained: *"I decided to come for work, not for entertainment. I was thinking of starting a family. Can you imagine someone aged 36 with no wife?"* (TunMig11).

Family relations in Tunisia are very strong, as well as responsibility for particular members of the family. Therefore, especially for settled and long staying migrants, who had often migrated slightly later in regard of age, than so-called newcomers, responsibility for the future situation of their kids was a very strong factor influencing the decision on migrating, as one of the interviewed women explains:

"Since I have children, I have to do everything for them. I worked in construction; I dug holes for olive trees. I even worked in coal mines. (...) The family got larger, and I don't own land or have work in agriculture. I have a small house, but I couldn't leave my children and go to work. I thought of a solution when the children started to grow, and this was to move to Sousse. (...) We locked our house and came here. We moved from a rented house to another. (...) [We came here because] I was thinking about my children. I hope they grow up, get married, and build villas near me. I was hoping they would become prosperous such as X and Y. (...) I wished that my sons would get a job, to be able to educate the other three or four. I have seen people who built houses, so I thought: why not me?" (TunMig03)

Living in a city is often connected with increasing responsibility for remaining family members, as one interviewee mentioned, stressing that:

"I learned responsibility. I am the oldest girl, so I feel responsible, I want to work and save money to help them because I am the oldest. They see that I am living in Sousse, I should help." (TunMig12)

"I am working with my sister and sending remittances to my father. We only keep our pocket money. We also work extra hours during the weekend. (...) We go home on Eid, or the new year and sometimes we get a week off during the summer." (TunMig10)

In general, those who leave want not only to earn money, but also to make some savings in order to finance their own projects. The idea of migration as one of the options for improving living conditions is very strong, as explained by one lady who, followed her husband to Sousse:

"We hold the idea that if someone wants to move, he needs to improve his life. We don't have job opportunities there and if we do, there is so much exploitation. If you work for a month, you only receive TND 300 (91.56 euros). You are obliged to accept the job. Those who move to Sousse, Tunis, or Hammamet want to work and save money. I was happy that he moved as I was thinking about studying and moving. I had a plan." (TuMigo4)

This need is so strong that young people are ready to move against the will of their parents, as one long-staying male migrant did:

My parents did not want [me to leave]. I was a teenager and wanted to start investing. They wanted me to stay there [in the region of origin]. My father wanted me to sell livestock and stay because he does not have savings in the bank. He works the land and has livestock. (TunMig15)

Reality, however, is different from ideals, as work in factories, even in Sousse, is not as profitable as expected.

"Most of those who come to Sousse work in factories. This is their utmost ambition. I've seen this with the people who work with me. They are struggling and earning 500 dinars (150 euros). They rent a house on their own, but

they are struggling, and they just want to work because in the rural part of Kasserine they can't. At least, they are surviving here even if they are not saving. (...) There isn't one who does not want to invest and live a better life, but we can't. Life is getting more difficult; it is stagnating, and people do not have money. There is much unemployment and some workers get dismissed from factories. There is no money circulation at all."
(TunMig16)

Education - used to give people hope

Another reason for migration is education either of the migrant him/herself or of family members. Time at school is often a period when expenditure for children arises. It is related not just with the costs of school as such (rarely any interviewee could afford private school) but also – and to a much greater extent - with expenditure for dorms and activities which, during the time when children are at school, *'made living conditions (...) harsh, especially on the financial side'* (TunMig19). For children from rural areas going to school was difficult due to environmental challenges and lack of adequate infrastructure as well, as one of the interviewees, already settled in the city, explained, describing her children's school:

"[it] was far, probably 3km. They also have to walk through clay and water. There is also an oued [river] and when it is active, they can spend up to one week without getting to school. You can see them walking in the rain and getting back home. Sometimes, their school bags get lost in the water and sometimes, we meet them to help them to cross the oued".
(TunMig22SF)

Therefore, boarding school was a necessity for many of those who did not live near a school. The associated cost was felt in the home budget. That is why as soon as children become old enough to start working, they were encouraged to do so, either in their spare time or to drop out of school altogether. One of our interviewees, pushed to work already in 7th grade, said:

"They helped me until I reached the 7th grade. Then, my father got me a job and I learned how to make money. I worked in a hardware store. In the past, 1 dinar and 3 dinars could do something. I used to get TND 30 per month. (...) I used to work in the summer when people were enjoying their time. I did that to save money to get clothes and finance my studies."
(TunMigo2)

Many of our respondents worked from early years and often (especially among youth) this work was undertaken alongside studying in town and cities. There was a 'tradition' of taking those girls who dropped out of school to work as maids in big Tunisian cities such as Tunis.

"They are used to work. They are not educated, they work as housemaids. I know many of them; my cousins (on my mother's side) are working there. The region is known for that, they come and take girls to work as maids. (...) I remember when I was young, there was a very well-known broker who came from Tunis with another woman and went to somebody's house where [the] daughter dropped out of school and [he] took her."
(TunMig10)

"It is not so common anymore as people now are more aware. They struggle but at least they study and achieve something".
(TunMig10)

In general, education, which is available in big cities, was for a long time perceived as a possibility for more opportunities and improvement of living conditions. One of the interviewees explained:

"In the past, many people, all Tunisians, were interested in agriculture and education. They only cared about the amount of rainfall and means of transportation. People there are aware and give much attention to education."

It means a lot for them to educate their kids. In terms of professions, the most popular one was commerce. More than 80% of the population are working in commerce. 20% have a Baccaureate, [it] is an achievement to succeed and earn a college degree."

(TunMig23)

"Almost 90% of young people finish their secondary education in Hajeb Al Ayoun. If they dropped out, they would end up working in construction or factories in Sousse, Sfax, or Tunis, i.e. big cities"

(TunMig19NM)

All families tried to support the education of as many members as possible. Often the eldest siblings dropped out of school to earn for the education of the youngest.

"Our conditions started to change when my eldest brother dropped out of school at an early age and started working. (...) earning money was the primary reason [for his dropping out] since the six of us go to school. He was not very good at school, so he preferred to drop out."

(TunMigo19)

The situation has changed, however, and education does not work as a trampoline anymore. 'It no longer gets you anywhere' (TunMig16), says one of the interviewees and another explains further:

"[Education] used to give people hope. Everyone went to school even those who couldn't afford it wanted to study to challenge poverty and help their families. When younger generations see me, and people like me unemployed, they don't move further, they look for training to learn skills. Education is beginning to stagnate."

(TunMig24)

This conforms that the data presented earlier in the report, that unemployment rate of higher education graduates is double of general average, are vivid among our respondents as well. Nonetheless, motivation for achieving higher education is still very strong:

"I decided to study in a different region, maybe in Tunis. I wanted to experience something new. I could have studied in Gabes or Sfax, which is closer to me. But I decided to go further, even though I felt homesick. I wanted to see different people."

(TunMig20)

Currently, the changing self-awareness of young women as they are striving to be independent and uncontrolled by their family, relatives and even neighbours, increases in significance as a factor motivating for migration. Social pressure can be very frustrating for both migrants and their families, as described by one young interviewee:

"(...) my father always supported me, despite all the problems, he even told me about some I hadn't known about. (...) I did not make him suffer, but people made me feel I did. My mother is also very sensitive, she does not want to hear anything from the neighbours, like 'don't let your daughter spend time with her friend, her friend is bad'. They also gossip with my brother and tell him not to let me dress in a particular way or go to a specific place. (...) I didn't want to work and then go back there. My problem is that I want to go away from that place and look for a job elsewhere. After Eid, I talked with my family and told them that I would not stay at home."

(TunMig25)

Education helps young women to achieve independence, as one female interviewee explained:

"I consider [tradition is the reason for] like 60% [of migration], because the girl there [in origin area] is under her uncle's or brother's control. She cannot do what she wants. We were raised on the principle that girls should not leave the house after the early evening prayer. If I need to recharge my phone, I cannot go out at that time. My

youngest sister calls me now to top-up her phone, because my mom does not let her go out at 8 pm, even though the supermarket is in the neighbourhood. This is the reason why many girls use education as a pretext to hang out with their boyfriends or fiancés. This is the reason so many girls left."

(TuMigo4)

Finally, people also move to cities due to abuses in their region of origin or a U-turn in their life, such as the death of the relative who was the main breadwinner of the household as well as when they are no longer able to handle the situation in their region of origin.

Another interviewee, who explained his reasons for leaving his region of origin, summarises this well:

"Above all, the reasons were financial and economic. If there were job opportunities in my region, I would never leave my family and stay away from my parents to see them only once or twice a year. If working conditions and means of development were good, we would never have thought of leaving. In terms of education, there are no universities or schools in the countryside. Life there is primitive; a school, a dispensary, and a public tap. Now, it has developed, as water and electricity are available in houses."

(TunMig19)

'Agriculture is not profitable and there are no jobs in Oueslatia, which made [me] move' - environmental reasons

The environmental conditions in Tunisia are rarely mentioned as a direct reason for migration. However, most of our interviewees came from rural areas where agriculture used to be the main activity. In south, delegates *'half of the population work in agriculture especially in dates production'* (TunMig20), in the Northern and along the coast, work in agriculture is often focused on the cultivation of olive trees and vegetables. Unfortunately, as indicated by one of the interviewed experts, agriculture is no longer perceived as profitable:

"Agriculture has become tough in recent years. It needs much patience and there is no patience now. Everyone wants to get rich overnight. This has led many people to stop working the land and migrate. Only a few stayed, there is the feeling of satisfaction that makes you patient. Most of them are young and the land used to be inherited which is no longer the case."

(TunExp1)

Land inheritance is not possible due to limited agricultural areas and the fact that land belonging to a particular family becomes smaller with each generation. An example of this was given by a lady from Kairouan, who pointed out that *"(...) a land that has 9 or 11 olive trees is nothing"* (TunMigo3SF). Another interviewee said:

"Conditions are poor there [in el Al'aa]; a great majority of people do not own land. There are some very rich people there but some others, whose fathers don't own land, start working at the age of 12. [One has no opportunities] unless one has land and a truck. One needs money."

(TunMig16)

Further explanation was given by a man from the same governorate:

"The only area available there is agriculture. If you inherit land and have financial resources, you can cultivate your land. Otherwise, you need to move to Sfax, Tunis, or Sousse, but in Hajeb Al Ayoun, this is not possible. It is a town surrounded by several rural areas where the only working domain is agriculture. If you have capital, you can work. If not, you should move to a different area."

(TunMig19NM)

Interviewees told us that they have decided to leave their area of origin even despite owning agricultural land. This is because the development of agriculture needs investments and capital. Thus, interviewees often

mentioned that, although they left their region of origin, they were sending remittances to support their family during the time watering or harvesting fields. A female interviewee explained the need for additional resources for watering, even though it is her father that is taking care of the land:

"We help him during the ploughing season or with irrigation, which needs money. Every month, each one of us [siblings] sends money because we do not have a brother to inherit it. We will get it all back. We need to cultivate the land. During the ploughing season, we need about a thousand dinars (circa 305 euros), which we collect together. I work now, so I can help."

(TuMigo4)

The challenge of limited resources, be it land or water, was mentioned in regard to different southern and internal governorates, such as Kasserine, Kairouan, Kebili or Tataouine where the number of crops depends on access to water resources, as one interviewee explained:

"When I was young, olive trees did not produce because there was no water. We also have apple trees. Farmers who own lands there [in Sbiba, Kasserine governorate] cultivate apple trees; they have wells. Those who do not have water cannot have fertile land."

(TunMig24)

Interviewees also indicated that lack of adequate support from the authorities, especially in regard to access to water in southern governorates makes this situation even more challenging. One female interviewee explained the reason for lack of income from agriculture both in the past and now:

"There is no support from the government. If you dig a well, they tell you that digging a deep well is illegal, yet they want you to work the land. If you dig a deep well, they can object and tell you to dig a medium-depth one of 25 metres, not a deep one. They tell you that this would affect the water table, and farmers cannot work the land without water."

(TunMig14)

Sufficient financial and water resources make it possible to achieve significant income. For instance, an interviewee from Kebili said: 'Those who have many palm trees can make 50,000 or 100,000 dinars (15,000 to 30,000 euros) or even more. They can make money out of it but they also spend a lot on water and palm wrapping' (TunMig20). Therefore, in order to live from agriculture, you need to have money for both life and development:

"In the countryside, it is good and bad, but those who have the means, such as a salary and a car, can live there. If you have land, you should have an income to live on. Living in the countryside is good if you have the means."

(TunMigo6)

Investments may, however, also cause inequalities among inhabitants of a region as in Kebili, where there are deep wells from which water is extracted with the use of pumps:

"There is a problem of water scarcity. Some are working without solar energy, but it is normal for others. Solar energy is very water-consuming, which makes it a struggle for others to obtain. There is no equity. [The income of those who have solar energy] can reach 20 thousand dinars (6 032 euros)."

(TunMig20)

One of the options for finding means for agriculture development is migration. A male interviewee mentioned in his testimony that in his childhood his father worked in other regions of Tunisia. Only after retirement and when the children graduated he gained resources and "got land in front of the house which is still fertile". In general, "100% of the population that works in agriculture, has livestock, or grows olive trees, barley or wheat. There are no big projects." Usually, this is enough only for the family's needs, "to get profits from agriculture,

you need to have some techniques, experience in terms of crop types and irrigation. People who used to work in agriculture are not convinced about this. They only know how to open the tap and get water. Agriculture there is based on the support of the family” (TunMig23).

Another factor that influences living in areas of origin are changes in environmental conditions. When they deteriorate or when there are not enough resources to cultivate more profitable products it is easy for the general economic situation of families to worsen. One of the experts explained:

“Even difficult climate conditions influenced the situation, such as drought. Many problems are affecting agriculture and causing losses. Hence, they choose to migrate even if they gave birth to their children in the countryside. They migrate because of the difficult conditions.”

(TunExp1)

A woman from Kairouan presented an example, saying:

“[the household economic condition] depended on lifestyle back then. If he [her father] grew wheat, he would harvest it in the summer. He could sell some of it and save the rest. He could grow almonds and olives. We were living fine. I went to school until the second year of high school. I dropped out because of our economic condition and came to Sousse.”

(TunMig15SM)

Nonetheless, she mentioned that if only she had the feeling that her kids were well established, she would go back to her region of origin as the situation there has improved significantly and *‘all facilities are available there, some people built houses better than the ones here [in Sousse]’* (TunMig15SM). She also indicated that the biggest difference between her region of origin and other regions was that in the former people had boreholes as a source of water. In regions where agriculture started to develop investments (water drilling) were carried out. That causes some people to return and build new houses, which are often bigger and prettier than those in Sousse.

Finally, the environment is mentioned as a factor that pushes people to move also from urban areas affected by pollution, such as the cities of Gabes or Ezzouhour. Such a situation was even described in the press (Blaise, 2020).

Political reasons

While before the Jasmine revolution numerous Tunisians were imprisoned or forced to migrate for holding political views not accepted by the president Ben Ali and his RCD (Rassemblement Constitutionnel) party (one of the key political migrants was the leader of the Ennahda Movement Rashid Ghannoushi – Pędziwiatr 2015, 2019), this situation has significantly improved after the transition of Tunisia from authoritarianism to democracy.

None of our interviewees mentioned political reasons as a cause of post 2010 internal migrations or a key driver for external migration. Such a reason was indicated only in the testimony of one interviewee, who mentioned student strikes against the regime in 1982, which caused him to leave the country. This may change, however, after the events of July 2021, when president Kais Saied suspended the Parliament and the government and in the following months unconstitutionally appointed a new prime minister. This surely needs to be further observed and may require additional investigations that go beyond the time framework on the project.

4.3. Reasons for choosing a destination

As mentioned before, the majority of internal movements are from western and southern governorates to the so-called Sahel (coastal governorates). One of the interviewed experts explained that: '(...) the coastal areas have more job opportunities or irregular migration because if people are in Kasserine and migrate to Gafsa, nothing changes. There is no sea in Gafsa so it is useless. When they head to Sousse, Djerba, Zarzis, they can get a job. If not, they can easily migrate illegally' (TunExp06). Cities in regions of origin do not give as many opportunities for jobs as the coastal area, what was also indicated by some of our interviewees:

"Whether you like it or not, Sousse offers more job opportunities. You can work in hotels during the summer for instance. I wanted to work in Gafsa but my family did not want me to work in hotels."
(TunMig08)

"We have opportunities but there are differences between Sousse and Gabes. Sousse has more job opportunities. In Gabes, you may find a factory but not everyone can work there. (...) It is a different situation in Sousse now but in the past, there used to be many opportunities. Not only in Sousse but in all tourist areas. Internal regions are always marginalised."
(TunMig14)

In big cities those opportunities are easier to be found either in a company or as an independent worker as explained by another interviewee who was determined to leave the region of origin of his early years:

"I planned to come to Sousse even if I got my Bac, I would come and study here. I did my training here. (...) I would not depend on anyone to hire me and if I did not get a government-paying job, I would work independently."
(TunMig12)

The choice of destination depends on different factors, for many, however, geographical proximity plays a very important role. This was also mentioned as a reason for choosing a particular university, and district in Sousse. Almost all the migrants from Kairouan first settled in Taffela, although after a while some of them bought land in other districts of Sousse. The passage through Taffela or Bir Chebek (which is a popular area) seems to be necessary for settlement and is influenced by two factors: 1) its location close to the workplace, convenient for those who want to settle and build their own houses, 2) the low costs of land, as pointed out by an interviewee speaking about the Taffela district of Sousse: 'the land is cheap here; I was patient as my salary was only 50 dinars (15 euros)' (TunMig15). However, those districts are distant from the centre and do not really improve the living conditions of migrants, as explained by one of the experts:

"Even when moving to the city, they will settle in a region where conditions are very similar to their past ones. They do not hold degrees and have no professional experience to find a suitable job, to live better. They settle in an urban slum with difficult conditions."
(TunExp1)

Also, direct advertisements of a workplace motivate people to choose a particular destination. This works similarly to social connections as the employee provides housing as in the case of a woman from Ain Drahem:

"There are those who head to Tunis. We were looking for a job back then, but we couldn't find any. This factory was announced through the office of employment. We went there as it is a well-known factory. (...) the factory brought us here which is guaranteed. If someone is coming on his own, he will struggle to find a place to live. The factory brought us here, we worked and went back to the dorm. I built myself up, nobody helped me."
(TunMig10)

According to the results of the research conducted, cities also provide more opportunities to those who are willing to both continue their education and combine it with finding financial resources for it. The possibility to

continue education at university is, however, determined by qualification results. Therefore, the precise choice of a city is not always a person's first choice. This happened to a female interviewee who moved from Sbiba in Kasserine Governorate to Sfax but was not accepted when she wanted to continue her education there. She explained:

"I wanted to stay in Sfax, where my friends were. My father said: You have been in Sfax long enough. They did not understand that I was looking for a research master, and there were none in Sousse back then. There was only vocational one, but I wanted to pursue a PhD. When they did not select me in Sfax, I decided to go to Sousse rather than have a gap year"

(TunMig24)

'He wouldn't let me if my auntie was not here' – role of networks

Social networks serve both as factors influencing the choice of destination and a facilitation of the process of movement itself. Many interviewees indicated that their relatives in Sousse facilitated their first steps in the city by finding a new place for accommodation: *'they have someone who rents houses [near my sister], she told me to come'* (TunMig22), or a first job: *'I came to Sousse in the '90s. He [my cousin] had a project. In the beginning, I worked with him then by myself'* (TunMig14), and helping in other ways:

"I came to Sousse, where I knew our neighbour, a district chief. His daughter is my friend and works as a medical secretary. He told me about a vacancy and took my documents to the regional administration. I got a job in the hospital of Farhat Hached (a university hospital in Sousse)."

(TunMig18)

"(...) at first, my father worked in Monastir. Then my oldest brother passed the Bac exam and moved with him to study in Sousse. Then my sister got her Bac and joined them. I joined them later. I got my Baccalaureate and came to study English in Sousse. (...) I wanted to feel settled and reunited with my family, because we hadn't been living together as everyone was studying in a different place. Also, there are no universities in Djerba, so I had to leave."

(TunMig26)

Relatives in the city also help parents to make the decision to let their daughters move outside the family house, as they are 'worried about leaving a girl on her own, especially since he [father] is not here with me' (TunMig12), as in the case of a newcomer female interviewee who further explained:

"I first thought of coming to Sousse and which factor would facilitate this as I am the only daughter in my family, which makes their [my parents'] decision difficult. This factor is my auntie [mother's side], who lives here. (...) The first year I came here, I lived with my auntie, then moved to the dorm, then moved back to my auntie's house. (...) They [my parents] are also at ease knowing that when I finish my classes I go home. I don't hang out with friends. It is different to live with family rather than with other girls. They ask where I go. Even if you were sick, no one would take care of you." (TunMig12)

The same interviewee also underlined the role of relatives in facilitating the first period in a new city. In her case, it was a cousin who not only facilitated financial issues, but also showed her all possible options regarding education, as she explained:

"She [a cousin] lives here and knows various places. She told me to come and see the academy. They paved the way for me to come. It would be too much for my family to pay for rent, living expenses and education. I spared the trouble of paying rent."

(TunMig12)

Usually, such influence came from an older as well as from more experienced in work and education. Yet among our interviewees, there were also those who came under the influence of their children who settled first and

facilitated both accommodation and work opportunities for their parents. In the case of one respondent, his children came to the city to work at a very young age and he followed them around four years later. As he mentioned in his testimony:

"(...) only when my sons insisted that I move [from the area of origin to Sousse]. They told me to come and they would pay for everything. I closed my eyes and moved (...) they told me that they would not go back to our region (...) They became used to staying here."

(TunMig22)

4.4. Types of work performed at destination

'At least someone can work here and does not stay unemployed. If I settle in my region, I will always be jobless.'

(TunMig24LF)

Once a destination is reached, it is not always as ideal as expected. Some people cannot find jobs even in big cities like Sousse and stay jobless in terrible conditions (TunMig16). Others admit that work conditions are difficult as in the example of a young man who said: *'I wake up at 4 am and finish work at 8 pm. I bring vegetables from the market. I close at night and my father helps me sometimes. I go back home to sleep'*. Further, he admitted: *'it is stressful to deal with people. If you stay here for 30 minutes, you will see. They are good, but they cause trouble too. If they buy something, they don't pay for it, so you can wait for four or five months to get paid'*. He feels obliged to let people buy on credit if they can't afford it, as this is the way he was raised (TunMig16). Many interviewees made a huge effort to combine education with earning a living, as a young lady from Kef, who described her situation: *"I study in the morning and finish at 3 pm, then work at the beauty salon. I get 20% for helping with each client. I work during weekends then I work in the centre."* (TunMig12).

Many of those unskilled take part in the recycling industry. Collecting plastic bottles or different types of metal (not always in a legal way) have become type of industry in such districts as Roummaniya. The daily income directly depends on the 'equipment', whether person collects plastic bottles just by them self, or with the use of bike or motor with a small trailer.

Finally, there are those whose working conditions do not change significantly after arriving in the city. This is especially the case of those who performed jobs in different types of factories and moved within the factory industry.

Despite all these challenges, those who are determined and willing to work can find jobs in the city or start their own venture and become independent, and even support people who remained in their region of origin, as one Kairouan respondent describes:

"Now there are five of us working members in the family. My father is no longer working as he is old. We launched small projects; we have livestock we invested in using our savings, and we started these projects to raise livestock and sell it on Eid to earn extra money. We used to need money from our father, now we all work and earn our wages."

(TunMig19)

4.5. Future migration intentions - return, stay or further migration

Our research indicates three major types of intentions among the persons that we have interviewed: to return to the places of origin, to stay where they are or to migrate further within the country or more popularly abroad. As far as the last type of intention is concerned some of our interviewees talked about the plan to migrate through legal channels, however many argued that for them the only truly "open option" is irregular migration. We start our analysis with the exploration of the least prevalent intention among our interviewees, that is to return to the place of the origin, and then move on to analyze much more frequently indicated

motivations in the collected data, to stay or to migrate.

4.6. 'Whichever place we go to, we should always come back' - Intentional Returnees

Some of our interviewees admitted that they were willing to leave their region of origin and Tunisia from the very beginning. One lady said: 'I've intended to leave ever since I was young. Leave Tunisia, not only Sers' (TunMig12), and another interviewee told us of her relatives:

"There are so many people like my cousins. All of them left, we meet only during Eid. They are in Tunis or Djerba; especially those from between 30 and 35 years. They get married and leave with their wives. They have children, live, and invest away from their region."

(TunMigo4)

Others, however, admitted that they left the region of origin to improve their situation and that of their relatives, and in general, were willing to go back as soon as possible to start their own business. Such statements appeared very often among our interviewees: *"When I speak with my friends, they say they want to come back and settle in El Oueslatia and it's the same for me. Whichever we go to, we should always come back."* (TunMigo5).

Sometimes the prospect of return regards the closest possible future, as in the case of the persons mentioned above, in others, it can come in retirement, as in the example of an interviewee who explained the approach she shared with her husband:

"He [my husband] is settled here and cannot go back to his region of origin. At the same time, when we got married, he built a house on top of his family's house and he is thinking of investing there [in his region of origin]. When I talk to my husband, he says that like migrants abroad, he needs to work here and invest in his region. It is because he cannot earn money there even if he has agricultural land. The living conditions are good. He says that living in Sousse is like living in France since he is making money. He will invest this money in building a house in his region of origin. He is now working and earning for rent, water, and electricity and the rest is for building the house."

(TuMigo4)

Interestingly this interviewee had also her own business plans regarding the place of origin. She argued that "Yes, I want to go back but not now, until I finish the plans I came for ... I want to launch my kindergarten in Gabes to go back there but this will be after preparing the project and finances. Also, I need to finish my house and not rent a house anymore. I need to do a project to survive" (TuMigo4).

In the case of some of the interviewees, the plan to return is not so much linked with any investment in the places of origin but rather with a very vaguely expressed wish of returning one day in the future to the village or town of origin, as reflected on this by one of interviewees: "I will leave this house to my children and go back there once I retire" (TuMigo3). In that sense, it takes the character of broadly explored in the migration literature the "myth of return" originally developed by Dahya (1973) and Anwar (1979) analysing the situation of Pakistani immigrants in Great Britain. Similarly, to the diasporic context the wish to return to a place of origin (sometimes fulfilled only after someone passes away) acts as an emotional and symbolic tie important for their identity and a cohesive force consolidating the family or kinship relations between those who left the places of origin with those who stayed. If no family or friends stay in the places of origin, then it frequently connects simply with landscapes and past memories.

Intentional and Forced Stayers

Much more prevalent among our interviewees was the intention to stay in Sousse after the initial internal

migratory move. The stayers could be broadly divided into two groups – those who intentionally want to stay and those who feel forced to stay by different factors - family, economic or professional ones being the most frequently mentioned.

As far as those who intentionally want to stay, it is above all those who are strongly anchored to Sousse and who are satisfied with the living standards they have managed to achieve in the city. Most frequently these kinds of answers we were hearing from the interviewees who had moved to the city at least a few years ago and integrated well into its economic and social structures, those who were comfortable with their jobs and salaries they obtained for them. One of the interviewees who fell into this category said: *'When you are comfortable in a place, there is no point in changing it. I am already a migrant, I am not in my home town'* (TunMig09).

One of our interviewees argued that if the Tunisian authorities were more successful in providing job opportunities, the number of stayers would overpass those who want to leave Tunisia. He pointed out that:

"If the government invests more in sustainable development, then people would improve their financial situation. Then, people would rather work in their home country rather than migrate. If the financial support is provided to live here, why would people migrate abroad? (...) If the economic situation improved in Tunisia, there would be no reason to migrate abroad except for tourism"
(TunMig19).

Some of stayers do not want to leave because they do not believe that a "better life" awaits them elsewhere. One of our interviewees argued that all that awaits many Tunisian irregular migrants to Europe is that 'they will drink and consume drugs then get to prison' (TunMigo2), so according to him they would be better off if they did not leave. Another interviewee argued that she would not like to move abroad to Europe because she would find it difficult to adapt to new life in a new place. She pointed out that *"I like it, but I don't think it would fit my personality. I don't feel comfortable and I do not adapt. As for tourism, yes, I would like to discover but for a long stay, it is difficult."* (TuMigo4).

Some of the persons we spoke to in Sousse said openly that they do not want to leave the city and the country because they are very strongly attached to them and cannot imagine themselves leaving what is for them the dearest – in spite of all the problems. One of them was a man in his mid-40s who when asked whether reflected migration answered in the following way: *'No, Tozeur is my limit. I love this country a lot'* (TunMig15). An oasis town close to the Algerian border (and another oasis town – Nafta) was the furthest place he could imagine migrating and nowhere abroad.

The broadly understood "family situation" has been one of the most commonly mentioned anchors that were forcing internal migrants who once came to Sousse to abandon plans for further migration. One of our interviewees who said that the family anchor was for him very important and that it strongly influences his decision in this matter was a young man who has lived in Sousse for over 10 years. He argued that: *"I don't want to leave my family and my mother. I got an opportunity to migrate legally abroad. The offer matched my job skills, but I said no"* (TunMig17).

Another interviewee, who despite having her sister abroad and was very firmly stating that she was not interested in the migration, was a woman who had lived in Sousse for five years. She stated that she would not like to migrate because she would not be able to leave her mother. When asked about the possibility of migrating she pointed out that *'I hate to be away from my family. Even here, I feel I am very far away from them. I would love to stay in my own place because I am so close to my family'* (TunMigo1).

Here it is also worth mentioning that although Tunisian society, by regional standards, is fairly liberal, women face more constraints when it comes to migration than men. In that sense, patriarchy acts as an important break to the mobility of some Tunisian women. It seems this phenomenon concerns more women living in

small towns and villages rather than those from the big cities. One of our interviewees who pointed this out argued that:

"Even if my family from abroad invited me, my father would not let me go. He was in France but did not stay for too long. He went home to get married to my mother. I had the right to go there in the past because my father was there, but he did not accept. He did not even let me apply for schools abroad. (...) My brother can migrate because he is a man. My sister got an opportunity to pursue a master's degree abroad, but he did not want to. How do I feel about it? I got used to it"
(TunMig20)

Another female interviewee, who complained about this issue, said:

"There are some who accept girls and women working outside of the home and others who don't. In our region, there are still conservative families. They refuse to let their daughters work away from home because they fear they would deviate."
(TunMigo1)

If it is not a broadly understood 'family' that forces people to stay in Sousse after the initial migration from the places of origin, then it is the effect of other factors among which important roles play current occupation and work. One of our interviewees who mentioned this impediment was working in the state sector in the security domain. He pointed out that:

"I cannot migrate due to my job. There is only one option which is to go on a mission. (...) I can get a passport, but I cannot travel unless I get permission from the general administration. I get permission requests to go to Algeria, France etc. The leave and travel are separate"
(TunMigo2)

Some of our interviewees suggested that migration is closely linked with certain phases of our life and that they were "too old" to consider any further migration. One of them when inquired about the intentions of migrations said: *"I wanted to stay in Sousse. I am old, I can't do it anymore"* (TunMig11). Another one while answering the same question pointed out that: *"It is no longer appropriate at the age of 50 to do something like this"* (TunMig14).

4.7. Prospective Regular Migrants

The major incentive behind the vast majority of cases of internal and external mobility of contemporary Tunisians is a desire to improve the quality of life. As one of the experts we interviewed has pertinently observed, the key pushing factor as far as both, internal and external migrations are concerned, is the lack of job opportunities. He argued that *"[s]ome young people reach 40 and are still living with their families and taking their pocket money from their parents because they are unemployed. Many families are complaining about this problem and want their children to go abroad."* The expert argued then that the families sometimes strongly contribute to migration including the illegal one and give money to their children to migrate (TunExp4).

A significant proportion of our interviewees and in particular those who have not lived in Sousse for an extended period of time, and hence fewer anchors, have further migration plans. Most of the time these are the plans to leave the country. Our interviewees spoke both about the channels of regular and irregular migration. As far as the first one is concerned, most frequently it is linked with educational plans or associated with professional work. A significant number of interviewees talked also about irregular migration and their perception of it. For many Tunisians who do not possess highly sought skills and qualifications this channel of migration – usually linked with crossing the sea on the boat or by overstaying on the tourist visa - is the only viable option. We first bring out elements of the collected data concerning the regular migration and then the irregular one.

One of our interviewees expressed the wish to emigrate from Tunisia within the upcoming year in the following way:

"If there is an opportunity to study abroad or any other opportunity. For me, if the opportunity is available, I am already looking for it" (TunMigo5).

At the same time, he has been also realistically assessing his chances as well as intellectual and social resources in the light of existing migration regimes. He pointed out:

"I hold a university degree and I speak the language (here meaning English). I can get a scholarship and travel. I have my friends abroad, but everything is related to migration policies. There could be opportunities sometimes but sometimes not".
(TunMigo5)

In this context, some of our interviewees brought up various scholarship schemes that allow the most talented and high achievers to go and study abroad. Erasmus-Socrates and Campus France probably being the most commonly mentioned. One of the experts we have interviewed pointed out that:

"There is a growing number of students that are migrating from big cities from universities in Sousse and other towns in Tunisia. You should not forget those who migrate through Campus France, either boys or girls. There is not only irregular migration but also student migration to European countries such as for example France and Germany".
(TunExpo4)

Some of our interviewees argued that *"(...) I would encourage someone to go abroad to study because education here is deteriorating"* (TunMig14) and thus linked the increasing number of Tunisians leaving to study abroad with decreasing quality of education in the country. Others, however, viewed it rather as one of the most viable strategies for migration, promising not only smooth economic but also social integration.

One of our interviewees working in the medical sector who wanted her daughter to study abroad saw this type of migration in negative terms as a form of brain drain. She pointed out:

"We have nothing left here. That is why Tunisia is lagging behind. All the brains are there abroad. They are lucky, but we just gave away all of our youngsters. If Tunisia had the means, we would have preserved doctors and engineers"
(TunMig18)

The opposite view on the migration of students and professionals expressed one of our experts who argued that: "Yes, many students are currently migrating, but it is not a brain drain since those who will study abroad will get their legal documents and end up integrating" (TunExpo4).

Some of the countries that were most commonly mentioned in the context of regular, educational and professional migration were: France, Germany, Switzerland, Belgium, Canada, USA as well as the oil-rich countries of the Gulf, in other words, those most popular destinations of international migration of Tunisians. One of the experts we have interviewed in the course of the research argued that:

"Those who do not hold any academic diplomas usually choose to migrate illegally most commonly to Italy. People who hold legal documents choose a better destination such as Switzerland, Germany, or the United States".
(TunExp2)

Important destinations for regular migrations are also neighbouring Libya and Algeria. The first one was an important destination before the Arab Spring but after the removal of Muammar Kaddafi and the beginning of political and military clashes, Libya became an emigration rather than immigration country (numerous Libyans

escaped war-torn regions and sought refuge in Tunisia). Their major advantage is proximity or as one expert expressed it *"because it is easy to move in and out of them"* (TunExp6). In the case of the mobility between Tunisia and Algeria-Libya, one may argue that Ernest Ravenstein's classic observation that the majority of migrants move a short distance has up until today some relevance. In the Arab world, some attractions also hold Gulf countries, which however have a very strict migratory policy and where migration is regulated through short- and long-term contracts.

The most important destination remains Europe though. As one of the interviewed experts has put it:

"Europe is always the first destination because since the second world war a migration tradition towards Europe has been created. Living standards and politics in Europe differ. People enjoy equal rights with high income, this is why it remains the sole destination. France is the first destination together with new destinations such as Italy, Germany, Portugal or even Poland and Spain but with little percentage".
(TunExp04)

The choice of Europe is clearly also strongly linked with the existing diasporic-migration networks. The places of the highest concentration of Tunisians such as France, Italy, Germany have their clear advantages. After them come Algeria, Libya, Gulf countries and Canada (TunExp06).

One of the interesting phenomena that sit in between the regular and irregular migrations is the mobility linked with marriage with a foreign citizen. Our research data mentioned this usually with relation to Tunisian men marrying non-Tunisian women (rarely in the opposite way), in order to be able to migrate legally to Europe or in the context of legalization of the irregular passage.

The case of gaining legal right to enter Europe was mentioned by the following interviewee who argued that getting married to a foreign woman is not illicit. He argued that *"some people pay to be on a sham marriage for two or three months. She gets paid for it so there is no exploitation"* (TunMig16). Sometimes, however, this arrangement is not purely a financial one but is built on some emotional investment of at least one person.

Another case of using marriage for legalization purposes after the earlier irregular entry into a given country was mentioned by the following interviewee. She accounted for the story of her brother who was helped by some Italian family when they found him sleeping rough on the streets of the town. *'The Italian man arranged a sham marriage for him to get his immigration documents. My brother contacted my cousin who works in the Ministry of Internal Affairs to get his passport through the embassy. He became a legal immigrant thanks to the Italian guy'* (TunMigo6).

Yet a different trajectory of legalization of irregular passage was pointed out by the interviewee who said that *'Those aged 16 or 17 are kept in an asylum centers and taken care of. When they get older, they plan for a sham marriage to get their legal documents'* (TunMig21). This interviewee mentions an important phenomenon of the growing number of minor asylum seekers from Tunisia that will be explored further below who, according to her, also try to legalize their status through marriage.

The marriage as a path to Europe might also involve the emotional involvement of both parts and might be arranged within the diasporic networks. Such a case was mentioned by another interviewee who described in the following way the situation of her cousin:

"He migrated illegally from the industrial zone of Gabes. He has friends working at the port. He sneaked into one of the merchandise ships. It is a luxurious way to migrate illegally. He reached Italy then moved to France. He struggled because we do not have many families, members around. (...) After migrating, he worked everywhere to survive. He also worked with people from Ghomrassen and Tataouine (cities in the south). They own houses in France. He became friends with his boss's sister. He was arrested in France, so she released him and he wanted to marry her. She has a minor disability. Her brother preferred to check whether this person is really in love with his

sister or wanted money. He said that he loved her. Her brother said that you should commit to her not getting the documents and leave her. He said that he loved her, and she helped him. She ended up coming to Tunisia to meet the family. His father felt that his son is looking for the money and the documents. After receiving his documents and having two children, they got divorced”.

(TuMigo4)

4.8. “The sea is available for everyone” – Prospective Irregular Migrants

If the aforementioned cases linked with migration through marriage or legalization of stay in a given country through marriage might have many elements of regular migration our research data included numerous accounts of the desire to make irregular passage to Europe as well. This type of migration is usually undertaken when all the possibilities of legal migration are exhausted.

As we have shown earlier there is an increasing number of people who are ready to even risk their lives at sea to reach Europe in an irregular way.

One of our interviewees who was ready to take the perilous journey through the sea said:

“If I find a guaranteed illegal migration, I would go. Guaranteed means I would not drown in the sea. My niece-in-law immigrated illegally with her husband and arrived safely to Italy, then left for France”.

(TunMigo6)

Many of our interviewees spoke also about the members of their close family who have either tried the irregular migration or expressed the desire to take the perilous journey through the sea to Lampedusa (the most common destination for Tunisian irregular migrants) or other places in Europe. One of the interviewees spoke about her brother who wants to migrate irregularly to Europe *“but we are not letting him go. My mother told him she would never forgive him”* (TunMigo8) At the same time our interviewee claims that irrespective of the mother’s protest he still thinks about it. She points out that *“he did not do well in education. He dropped out in the 8th grade and was subject to peer pressure. I brought my family here for the sake of my brother. I wanted him to get a job. He has been working with the carpenter. He at least gets money to purchase clothes”* (TunMigo8).

Yet another interviewee accounted for the experience of irregular migration of one member of the family in the following way:

“My brother-in-law migrated illegally but was expelled in the middle of the trip. He is 31 years old and went to Jerjis to migrate from there with his friends. In the past, the idea of illegal migration was not very common. His older brother is the supervisor of the police station in Gafsa and urged him to stay or get a contract to migrate legally. His friends pushed him to go with them. They told him that it is an opportunity to take now. The organizer of this illegal migration told them that they will be given temporary entrance papers. He was also assured because we have a family there. By the end, everything was a lie and he was facing death. When he was working, he was earning at least 1500 Tunisian dinars. (...) When he was away my husband got a phone call from his mother about his brother migrating illegally and that he was not calling them for two weeks. That week was like hell. My husband was only smoking and not eating. Eventually, it turned out that he spent three days in the sea and was returned. The captain did not know the way. They asked whether they would go home or die in the sea. (...) He borrowed 3 thousand dinars from my mother-in-law, and he did not give them back. The pressure was on my oldest brother-in-law who works in the police station. He talked to the organizer of the illegal migration to get the money back. They met all four. My brother-in-law grabbed them all in the car and took the money.”

(TuMigo4)

The irregular migration from Tunisia has been increasingly involving also minors and women. As the last report of the Italian Association for Legal Studies on Migration (ASGI) from June 2021 shows every year the number of Tunisian minors reaching Italy is growing. Since 2016, more than 12,000 migrant children have been

placed in hotspot facilities in Lampedusa, Messina, Pozzallo, Trapani and Taranto (ASGI 2021: 8). Unlike adult migrants, unaccompanied minors cannot be returned. Some Tunisian media report on children threatening to take their own lives if their parents do not help them pay for the smugglers who will arrange their crossing over the sea (Khdeir 2021).

As one of the interviewed experts has put it bluntly: *"Those who want to migrate legally can get a job contract, otherwise, the sea is available for everyone"* (TunExp06). In recent years due to volatility of the economic situation of the country - first hit by the wave of terrorist attacks targeting politicians, citizens and foreign tourists, and then by the pandemic – the increasing number of people have been resorting to perilous irregular migration to Europe by the sea. As our interviewee argued:

"The pandemic of Covid-19 has impacted the economic situation of the country (...). Many people ended up losing their jobs. They used to work and get a salary but ended up unemployed, so they will resort to the sea. They have no hope to get a job. Also, competitions have stopped since 2019. When you talk to them, they have no solution even those who used to be working ended up jobless. In Jerjis, every day we hear about people leaving. There are new ways of irregular migration. (...) They use a big jet. In 4 hours, you will be in Lampedusa, it is no longer a boat of 80 people. The jet is fast.

(TunExp06)

To sum up this part of the report it is worth quoting yet another interviewee who has captured the gist of many of the aforementioned opinions and stories. He has pertinently argued that:

"Illegal migration is a form of expression because someone who is migrating in such a way has a message to deliver. He is escaping the country because there is a problem. Why did he leave his country for another one? What does he want? It is not because he likes to live like Europeans - he can do that in Tunisia. There are some who seek asylum such as religious and gender minorities. It is a big question. Many people are victims of gender violence in a society that disdains differences; for instance, homosexuals are not accepted. Then, they will seek an opportunity abroad to look for diversity and freedom. (...) Still, economic and educational reasons are the major reasons to push people to migrate".

(TunMig05)

4.9. Differences between past and present

Looking closer at the differences between past and more current movements in Tunisia, we can see that in the past, people travelled more often and for shorter periods of time. 'They headed to Sousse, Monastir, Kairouan, Sfax or Tunis to work for 10, 15 days, a month or two then went back home bringing a sum of money' (TunMig03). As time passed, the economic opportunities in the area of origin have become more limited, causing more people to leave permanently. This change was pointed out by many of our interviewees, e.g. the person who came to Sousse from Kairouan over ten years ago:

"The present generation is no longer satisfied with agriculture. They would prefer to stay in cities. Even in terms of education, they go to university more often than ever before. In the past, moving from one city to another was not frequent. When I first left, my parents came after me to bring me back, but my father became impressed that I was able to earn more."

(TunMig15)

Previous movements to cities were also often related to the willingness to improve the living conditions of the whole family without thinking about further movements to Europe or other destinations. The opportunities available while staying in a city can today facilitate further, international movements, including illegal ones.

The research also indicates that migration patterns change, especially regarding their gender aspect. Due to cultural reasons, past movements were carried out by either men or entire families. Currently, especially

in the case of some areas, *'the majority [of those who move] are girls. They move to the coastal region to work in factories, due to job availability'* (TunMigo1). As mentioned before, in today's movements, especially for women and young people, cultural and social factors - such as the desire for emancipation and empowerment, or to reunite with family members, e.g. partner or parents – are strong incentives. Even married women look for work opportunities more often, and so entire families move in order to find jobs for both spouses:

"Their wives cannot find a job here and stay home. They cannot provide everything by themselves, so they choose to go to Sousse, Tunis or Djerba. Their wives can get a job there and help each other. Also, people want to entertain, they want to go out in the summer. In Sousse, they are close to Mahdia, or Tunis, while Gabes, they lose too much money renting an apartment or a hotel. They prefer to live, entertain, and educate their children in a different region."

(TuMigo4)

The economic situation in the past was frequently more difficult than at present. A common practice in southern and western governorates was that parents 'gave away their daughters to work in Tunis in order to receive remittances from them. Ain Drahem is a very poor region. Some people cannot even afford dinner. They [the daughters] get 150 dinars (45 euros) and send all of it to their families, since they live where they work' (TunMig10). A similar situation can be also found among our interviewees. A woman, who came to the city at the age of 12 explained:

"I came here to work. My father died, and my mother married another man. I came here to live in my auntie's house in Bir Chobbek (a slum in Sousse). I worked as a maid and then met this man and got married."

(TunMigo7)

Picture: Karin Bem Van/Unsplash.com

5. Conclusions

The aim of the research carried in Tunisia, particularly Sousse city, was to examine migration trajectories where cities potentially are a stepping points towards further international migration. We were also looking at changes in migration patterns in time periods trying to compare three groups of internal migrants: those who came to Sousse up to 5 years, between 5 and 10 years and over 10 years ago.

The interviews conducted with 29 internal migrants and 5 experts indicate that reasons for leaving the origin region are varied. Certainly, the search for work remains the main cause due to which the majority of our interviewees left their homes. But there are other factors at play, such as for example educational ones. For women and young people, there are also cultural and social factors, such as the desire for emancipation and empowerment, to reunite the family by joining a partner or parents. Some participants stressed environmental problems, such as pollution or water shortage. Generally, personal aspirations are intertwined with the economic, social and political context of the region of origin which confirms the preliminary approach on complexity and multicausality of factors influencing migrations.

Key factors shaping the internal and external migration flows of Tunisians are linked with the state of the country's economy. Some of the sectors that were key elements of it – such as tourism – have suffered enormously at first from terrorist attacks targeting foreigners and then the Covid-19 pandemic which additionally increased already high level of unemployment that is particularly severe among highly educated youth.

Our results indicate, however, that we should not look only at the push and pull factors that were presented in one of the most common theory, but we should also consider a wide range of factors that influence the process of migrants' decision-making such as the role of the family and regional and cultural attachment and social networks. The aforementioned factors were suggested by our interviewees as those that kept them in the Sousse city, as well as created dreams of future return to the regions of origin.

The choice of Sousse was justified mostly by the distance, social networks (most important family who at the beginning could take care of a moving woman), education possibility and finally, opportunity to find employment in industry sector. Sousse rarely was perceived as stepping point towards further movement to Europe at the moment of departure from the region of origin. Only lack of prospects for future in Sousse and in Tunisia in general, makes the pressure to international migration, especially among youth, stronger than among the past generations. As pandemic influenced the Tunisian economy it has forced even more people than in the past to envisage to migrate irregularly to Europe (most commonly through Italian Lampedusa) through the Mediterranean Sea or, particularly among students and highly skilled, to look for legal options either educational or through arranged marriage.

As a recommendation from this research regarding the issue of irregular migration, the EU should open the channels of legal economic migration not only to those highly-skilled but also to those less skilled (e.g. through the system of lottery like the US green cards). More attention should be also given to variety types of development activities in different regions of Tunisia that will on the one hand decrease the regional development differences and on the other hand deliver employment options in the regions of origin, decreasing firstly pressure on internal and then international migration. Additionally, the development of the political situation in Tunisia should be further observed, as interrupted democratic transformations of Tunisia may lead to deterioration of economic situation and increasing emigration pressure. There might also be an increasing number of persons leaving the country for political reasons.

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